

6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured and twinning enabled Open experimentation facility

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ABSTRACT

This report outlines the implementations of technology enablers within the 6G-SANDBOX Library, including Open RAN, RIS, NTN, Deterministic Networking with P4 and TSN, as well as XR. In the context of our EU project, the "6G Library V1" deliverable aims to create the foundational version of the 6G Library. This involves explaining the concepts, roles, and implementation of disruptive technologies like Open RAN, RIS, NTN with OpenSAND, Deterministic networking with P4, Time-sensitive networks, and extended reality (XR). The key objective is to outline how these technologies are implemented in the contexts of 6G, emphasizing connectivity with the API, Experimentation automation tools, Trial Networks, and the 6G library repository throughout their lifecycle. The relevant 6G library objects are also mentioned to indicate their useability. An established Library repository will be utilized in the development process, with a concentration on the latest technology components and their integration. A detailed methodology covering the Research Approach, Data Collection, results, and Data Analysis for the pertinent technology components is provided in Section 3. This methodology aligns with the goals of the broader "6G-SANDBOX" project, as explained in Section 3 of Deliverable 2.1. At a higher level, the 6G-SANDBOX facility is envisioned to grow into the complete 6G library, aligning seamlessly with the overarching project objective.

KEYWORDS

Open RAN (O-RAN), Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS), Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), Time Sensitive Networking (TSN), Extended Reality (XR).

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

Section 2 "Technology Enablers" presents the concepts and significance of the following disruptive technologies such as open RAN, Non-terrestrial networks (NTN), Reconfigurable intelligent Surface (RIS), extended reality (XR), deterministic networking – network programming with P4 and time sensitive intelligent traffic scheduling. It also describes these technologies' roles in the creation of the initial version of the 6G library.

Section 3 "Implementation of Technology Enablers" explains how to implement these disruptive technologies. These include HW and SW components, deployment scenarios and use cases, initial results, and findings for the 6G Library. This section will also describe the 6G library objects including their parametric information, values, output values, and deployment results.

1.2 TARGET AUDIENCE

The 6G Library serves as the main framework that defines the key components and their capabilities, which should be available for the 6G-SANDBOX testbed or any replicated testbed. The deliverable's release is intended for public access, aiming to introduce the comprehensive 6G-SANDBOX facility to a diverse range of research individuals and communities. The identified target audiences for D3.2 span from specific to broader categories, encompassing:

- The primary audience involves the Project Consortium, tasked with validating the analysis of all objectives and proposed technological advancements. The deliverable ensures a thorough examination through the detailed description of technology enablers and the elucidation of their roles in achieving project goals.

- The Research Community and funding European Commission (EC) Organization are targeted to: (i) summarize the scope, objectives, and innovative aspects of the 6G-SANDBOX Library V1, (ii) provide a detailed account of the implementation of technology enablers, presenting initial results and findings, and (iii) illustrate integration approaches with the 6G-SANDBOX Library, offering insights into project innovations..
- The vertical actors that will be engaged to the project with the process of the open calls will utilize the 6G-SANDBOX facility to conduct their experiments.
- The public is a broader audience targeted to enhance their understanding of the framework and scope of the 6G Library within the 6G-SANDBOX project.

2 TECHNOLOGY ENABLERS IN 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

2.1 OPEN RAN (O-RAN)

2.1.1 CONCEPT AND SIGNIFICANCE

Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) are a transformative concept in the field of telecommunications that has gained significance with the development of 6G technology. O-RAN refers to a more open and disaggregated approach, initiated by O-RAN ALLIANCE to build and operate wireless networks, including radio access networks. It departs from conventional, unified network structures in which the hardware and software elements are tightly integrated and often come from a single vendor. The mission of O-RAN ALLIANCE [1] is to transform the Radio Access Network industry towards truly open, intelligent, virtualized and fully interoperable RAN. The main principles of O-RAN are to provide open interfaces of the RAN components with the alignment of Software-defined networking (SDN) [2] and Cloud-native technologies [3]. O-RAN uses open interfaces between the different components of the RAN, such as the radio unit (RU), centralized unit (CU), distributed unit (DU), and controllers. This enables network operators to combine and pair components from different vendors, which may result in reduced expenses and enhanced creativity. O-RAN uses the SDN paradigm to control and manage the RAN. SDN separates the control plane of the network from the data plane, which makes the network more flexible and scalable. Moreover, O-RAN uses cloud-native technologies, such as virtualization and containerization, to deploy and manage the RAN. This makes the network more efficient and cost-effective.

O-RAN is expected to play a significant role in the development and deployment of 6G networks. 6G networks are expected to be much more complex and demanding than 5G networks and O-RAN's flexibility, innovation, and cost-effectiveness will be essential for meeting these demands [4]. The following benefits could be realized from the deployment of O-RAN, e.g., Disaggregation and Openness nature of the network, interoperability, flexibility and scalability, lowering cost, and enhancing security. Open RAN promotes interoperability by defining open and standardized interfaces between different network elements. This allows for multi-vendor environments where different components from different suppliers can seamlessly work together. In 6G, where diverse technologies and devices are expected to coexist, interoperability is critical. Traditional network architectures often lead to vendor lock-in, where operators are heavily dependent on a single vendor for their network infrastructure. Moreover, O-RAN reduces this dependency, giving operators more flexibility to choose components and software from various vendors, promoting competition, and potentially reducing costs. By breaking down network elements into interchangeable components, O-RAN can potentially reduce the cost of building and maintaining wireless networks. This cost reduction can be particularly important for 6G, which is expected to be a complex and expensive network to deploy. O-RAN encourages innovation by enabling smaller vendors and startups to enter the market. This can lead to faster development and deployment of new technologies, which is crucial for 6G to stay at the cutting edge of wireless communication. In addition, it allows network operators to scale their networks more flexibly and efficiently. As 6G networks will need to adapt to various use cases, including massive IoT, ultra-reliable low-latency communication, and enhanced mobile broadband, flexibility and scalability are key.

Moreover, the role of open interface based wireless networks (e.g. ORAN) in developing the future network architectures and mechanisms contributes to exploitation and further enhancements of the features such as high level of programmability (e.g. various planes: control, data, telemetry, management), covering emerging features of the 3GPP standards beyond 5G hierarchy of control loops (real-time, near RT, non RT), scalable disaggregation of functionalities (service based RAN, Core), orchestration of AI/ML features and functions (control and data planes), cognitive plane availability (e.g. ETSI ENI/GANA or relevant), dynamic orchestration of security mechanisms (security as a service) etc.

2.1.2 ROLE IN 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

The software and hardware components related to disruptive technologies, such as O-RAN, will be delivered as part of the 6G-Library in the University of Malaga (UMA) platform. The aim is to enhance the disaggregated and virtualized architecture of O-RAN (vRAN) in the 6G testbed. This testbed is controllable and can be used as an experimental platform for open callers or experimenters. The implementation of O-RAN shown in Section 3.1.1 at the infrastructure facility layer of the testbed will serve as the foundation for the open and reusable 6G library in trial networks.

As a part of 6G-SANDBOX Library, O-RAN will be able to provide following features/objectives: O-RAN setup will encompass the delivery, installation, configuration, and integration of critical components, including O-CU, O-DU, Near-RT RIC, and xApps, along with the preparation of Docker/K8 files and the use of private registry Docker Hub/K8. This will focus on manual processes and compliance with minimal hardware and software requirements. Several APIs will be used to facilitate the integration of O-RAN as part of this implementation. These include IS-Wireless - Liquid RAN - Near-RT RIC; IS-Wireless - KPM xAPP; IS-Wireless - RC xAPP. Using this setup, 6G-SANDBOX will be able to test internal data transmission, interface test with other E2, and N2/N3 with the options of attaching another core etc. The workload prediction xApp specifically targets CPU workload forecasting within the O-RAN architecture. By anticipating CPU load, it enables proactive resource management, ensuring optimal CPU utilization and preventing bottlenecks during peak traffic periods.

From 2024 to 2027 and beyond, Open RAN (O-RAN) is set to play a transformative role in the development of 6G networks by fostering a more flexible, scalable, and efficient architectural framework. This paradigm shift away from traditional, vendor-locked systems towards an open, interoperable design enables greater innovation and diversity in network equipment and software sources. Within the scope of the 6G-SANDBOX Library, a crucial role is played by the development and implementation of a highly programmable control plane, wherein cutting-edge technologies such as xApp, RIC (RAN Intelligent Controller), and E2 interfaces are employed. This integral aspect ensures the creation of a dynamic and adaptable network infrastructure, facilitating seamless operation. Additionally, access to an extendable telemetry framework is provided, enabling comprehensive monitoring and data collection capabilities. This framework serves as a foundational element for informed decision-making and optimization strategies. Furthermore, a commitment exists to support the continual evolution and enhancement of Radio Resource Management (RRM) and other related algorithms and mechanisms. This commitment underscores the dedication to advancing the capabilities of the 6G-SANDBOX Library, contributing to the overall success and innovation of the EU project.

2.2 RECONFIGURABLE INTELLIGENT SURFACE (RIS)

2.2.1 CONCEPT AND SIGNIFICANCE

As 6G has been moving towards higher frequencies to obtain higher data rates, the challenge of working in the millimeter wave (mmWave) range (>24.45 GHz) is being faced by the entire industry. Signals in the mmWave bands are particularly affected by the environment, such as foliage, rain, people, glass and walls, and the free-space path loss (FSPL). For this project in particular, the FSPL needs to be accurately modeled to provide us with the information about how large a RIS needs to be to aid a mmWave channel. Moreover, as previously mentioned, high frequency signals are strongly affected by the surrounding environment and the presence of

an obstacle such as a building or a tree are enough to block communications. To circumvent this issue, an RIS can be used to efficiently redirect the signal with direct line of sight (LoS) from TX to RX.

The RIS is composed of an array of metallic elements, called unit-cell, which are controlled by switching devices such as PIN diodes, varactor diodes, etc. These components change the electromagnetic properties of the unit-cell and when controlled by a processing unit, reconfigures the reflection characteristics of the surface (hence the name, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface). When this is achieved, the RIS acts like a phased antenna array and can be beamforming, sending the signal more concentrated towards the user equipment (UE), compensating for the FSPL, and avoiding obstacles.

For the purposes of 6G-SANDBOX, each unit-cell is controlled by two PIN diodes, each responsible to switch the state for the vertical and horizontal polarisations (the axis in which the electric field is oscillating), therefore it presents 1-bit per polarization. The PIN diodes are responsible for changing the phase of the reflected wave by 180° between states and control the direction of the wave.

2.2.2 ROLE IN 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

The aim is to develop a RIS with a role to extend the coverage of a 6G testbed within the 27.05-27.50 GHz band, part of n257 (26.5-29.5 GHz) and n258 (24.25-27.5 GHz) bands. The RIS must be controllable from a remote site and be able to switch the phase of individual unit cells to scan the reflected beam. We therefore are following the sequence of steps below to achieve the desired performance of RIS:

- Electromagnetic (EM) characteristics of the PIN diode and modeling of a unit-cell to provide a 180° phase shift between the two states of the PIN diode across the n261 band.
- Based on the performance of the designed unit-cell, estimation of the channel path-loss to calculate the optimal size of the RIS.
- Develop the digital architecture of the RIS, which will be responsible for controlling the PIN diodes
- Determine how the Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) will manage the phase of each unit-cell depending on the desired characteristics of the channel.

As a part of 6G-SANDBOX Library, RIS can provide testing of the following:

- Signal Reflection and Manipulation in terms of (a) Reflectivity of the surface, (b) Ability to redirect signals in desired directions, and (c) Precision of signal focusing.
- Channel Gain Enhancement in terms of (a) Gain achieved by the RIS in terms of signal power or SNR (depending upon the receiver being in signaling or non-signaling mode) (b) Enhancement of signal strength in desired directions.
- Coverage Area in terms of (a) Maximum range of operation for signal enhancement, and (b) Area within which reliable signal enhancements are provided.
- Energy Efficiency in terms of (a) Power consumption levels, (b) Energy harvesting capabilities (if applicable), and (c) Adaptation of energy usage based on system requirements.
- Reconfiguration Speed in terms of (a) Time required for the RIS to adapt to changing signal conditions, and (b) Faster reconfiguration for dynamic optimization comparable with the channel coherence time.
- Interference Mitigation in terms of (a) Ability to nullify or minimize unwanted signals, and (b) Reduction of multi-path effects for improved signal quality.
- Scalability in terms of (a) Deployment in various environments and scenarios, and (b) Factors such as the number of elements, system complexity, and integration ease.
- Cost-effectiveness in terms of (a) Manufacturing costs, (b) Installation complexity, and (c) Affordability compared to alternative solutions.

2.3 NTN

2.3.1 CONCEPT AND SIGNIFICANCE

Non-terrestrial networks, including satellite platforms, play an important role in expanding 5G/6G connectivity beyond traditional terrestrial networks. The appearance of 5G and 6G technology has brought about a paradigm shift in wireless communication. Beyond terrestrial networks, non-terrestrial networks have become essential.

Non-terrestrial networks are instrumental in shaping the 5G/6G landscape, offering many indispensable functions that extend and enhance global connectivity. At the forefront, they provide a lifeline to remote and underserved regions, where terrestrial infrastructure deployment proves challenging. They become vital during times of crisis, ensuring disaster recovery and resilience through redundancy and emergency communication services, safeguarding connectivity even when natural disasters and network outages strike [5]. In addressing the digital divide, non-terrestrial networks stand as a beacon of hope, delivering high-speed broadband to remote areas, thus empowering communities with the digital resources necessary for education, healthcare, and economic growth. Furthermore, these networks provide a critical backbone for the expanding Internet of Things (IoT), supporting the connection of devices in remote or mobile environments. They enable low-latency communication, a prerequisite for latency-sensitive applications. Augmenting terrestrial networks' capacity, they ensure seamless connectivity during large-scale events and in densely populated areas. These networks also act as the vital backhaul links for remote terrestrial base stations, bridging gaps where fiber-optic infrastructure is absent. Finally, non-terrestrial networks contribute to real-time environmental monitoring, surveillance, and disaster management through the deployment of stratospheric platforms, ensuring rapid data collection and response in critical situations. In essence, non-terrestrial networks represent a cornerstone of 5G and 6G, elevating global connectivity and delivering essential support [6][7].

6G-SANDBOX platforms are integrating commercial NTN solutions as part of their infrastructure, with focus in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) constellations. This NTN infrastructure will be shared among Trial Networks in each platform, for example as backhaul connectivity or to test protocols like MPTCP. Besides the NTN infrastructure, 6G-SANDBOX Library will include a Satellite emulator as well, based on the OpenSAND solution, supported by the Athens platform (NCSRDI, INFOLYSIS), which will facilitate the agile experimentation of relevant use-cases.

Open Satellite Network Demonstrator (OpenSAND) is an open-source software designed to facilitate the testing and simulation of satellite communication systems (mainly DVB-RCS2 and DVB-S2). OpenSAND's primary purpose is to mimic the behavior of satellite networks, allowing users to assess the performance and reliability of their applications under various simulated conditions. Its versatility is further highlighted by its capacity to integrate with other simulation and network analysis tools, enhancing its utility in research and development efforts in the satellite communication domain.

2.3.2 ROLE IN 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

6G-SANDBOX project will explore advancements related with the use of aerial devices or flying nodes as new ways of wireless communications enabling new use cases- for example - the use of satellite connectivity as a beyond 5G backhaul or the integration of innovative protocols like Multipath TCP (MPTCP) or Multi-connection Tactile Internet Protocol (MTIP). The intention is to eliminate any distinction between terrestrial and non-terrestrial (NTN) elements, allowing for their seamless orchestration. This orchestration aims to create a cost-efficient network configuration that dynamically relocates functionality and establishes a flexible network topology.

In the 6G-SANDBOX initiative, our objectives are as follows:

1. **Efficient Implementation for Multi-connectivity:** We will focus on efficient implementation, aligned with SRIA 2021-27. This includes the utilization of MPTCP, the introduction of new Active Queue Management (AQM) algorithms, the integration of the QUIC transport protocol, innovations in Explicit Congestion Notification (ECN) usage, and the adoption of new transport protocols like the MTIP proposed by University of Malaga (UMA).

2. **Design of New End-to-End Protocols:** In response to the challenge presented in SRIA 2021-27, which centers on "enabling dynamically mapping the service needs of applications to the current network infrastructure," we will design and develop new end-to-end protocols. These protocols will provide support for dynamically aligning application requirements with the existing network infrastructure.
3. **Incorporation of Real and Emulated Satellite Nodes:** The experimentation process in 6G-SANDBOX will involve both real and emulated satellite nodes. Additionally, we will provide APIs to service developers that will be jointly orchestrated through AI-based algorithms. This orchestration will make use of virtualized network functions that can be dynamically deployed across both terrestrial and non-terrestrial nodes in a distributed manner.

This approach is aimed at achieving a more integrated, efficient, and adaptive network configuration that leverages the strengths of both terrestrial and non-terrestrial elements, ultimately advancing the capabilities and potential of 6G networks.

As a part of 6G-SANDBOX Library, NTN will be able to provide testing of the following:

- Satellite backhaul for 5G/6G networks
- Support for multi-connectivity (MPTCP, MTIP, ETC)
- NTN experimentation in trial networks
- Performance testing using different TX solutions
- Evaluation of maturity through some defined KPIs of different NTN providers (Starlink and OneWeb) for the initial use cases in 5G or 6G networks
- Multi-link backhaul with the ability to switch on-demand between satellite and terrestrial links.

2.4 DETERMINISTIC NETWORKING – TIME-SENSITIVE NETWORKING INTELLIGENT TRAFFIC SCHEDULING

2.4.1 CONCEPT AND SIGNIFICANCE

In the context of 5G/6G networks, deterministic communications offer high reliability and predictability for data transmissions, in which the information is sent and received with minimal latency and jitter. Therefore, this concept is expected to play a crucial role in the development of 5G/6G networks and their services and applications. In addition, it encompasses a certain number of features, including the following:

- **Low latency/jitter and predictability:** One of the main objectives is to provide a minimum bounded latency, which offers a high level of predictability. In addition, this also leads to low jitter values.
- **Reliability:** Mechanisms are in place to improve reliability and ensure that communications have a very low percentage of packet loss. This makes it possible to run applications on this type of network where data integrity is vital.
- **Time-sensitive applications:** Time-sensitive applications such as real-time control systems, immersive experiences and critical infrastructure management are increasingly in demand. Deterministic communication ensures that data is delivered within a predefined time frame, which is crucial for these types of applications.

In addition, other concepts such as network slicing, which allows using the same physical infrastructure to have several virtual ones, as well as Quality of Service (QoS) to guarantee the strict quality requirements imposed by the traffic, make it possible for the network to be optimized for use cases with completely different requirements. Consequently, deterministic communications enable 5G/6G networks to support a wide range of users and applications, including emerging applications with different requirements and quality levels. This allows sectors such as automotive, manufacturing or healthcare to benefit from the use and performance of these networks.

However, the implementation of deterministic networking poses several challenges. The unpredictability of network traffic and environments and the accurate network Quality of Service estimation for a given network configuration makes it complicated to deliver deterministic communication to the emerging time-critical applications. Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods, e.g., deep learning, reinforcement learning, federated learning, bring new opportunities to ensure the deterministic QoS provisioning in a large-scale network. AI-based network management framework should also be devised and leveraged to perform network control and configuration by utilizing intelligent network monitoring, analyzing and scheduling technologies, so that the deterministic network behavior and network performance could be guaranteed and delivered to the end users.

2.4.2 ROLE IN 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

The objective is to provide deterministic communications on the Malaga platform. The Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) testbed available on the Malaga platform is expected to be remotely accessible, including TSN bridges and endpoints. On the one hand, Figure 1 presents the wired TSN configuration architecture. This configuration is composed of:

- TSN endpoints: final devices in charge of sending (called talker) and receiving (called listener) traffic.
- TSN Bridges: particular Ethernet switches capable of transmitting TSN traffic
- Centralized Network Configuration (CNC): device responsible for managing and configuring the network settings and parameters
- Centralized User Configuration (CUC): device focused on user-specific configuration for different services requirements

This architecture allows the extraction of statistics from the switch ports, as well as the configuration of the main TSN characteristics (802.1AS: time synchronization, 802.1Qbv: scheduled, traffic, 802.1Qav: forwarding and queuing, etc.).

Figure 1. TSN architecture [11]

On the other hand, it is possible to combine the TSN network with the 5G network available in the Malaga platform, resulting in the TSN wireless configuration depicted in Figure 2. To enable this configuration, it is necessary to provide TSN translators, Device-Side TSN translator (DS-TT) and Network-Side TSN translator (NW-TT), which will perform the functions defined in [11] for compatibility between both domains, as well as the TSN Application Function (TSN AF), which is in charge of the mapping of the information (including QoS) and configuration of TSN through CNC and 5G network.

Figure 2. TSN over 5G architecture [12]

In addition, an intelligent deterministic network management framework will be established for the network operation and management (O&M) and optimization. In the proposed intelligent analysis and decision framework, the monitoring system will collect and analyze the characteristics of time-sensitive flows and network statistics to enable data-driven network analysis and prediction. Then, based on the information and knowledge abstracted from the underlying networks, the analyze engine will leverage the queuing theory or network calculus tools to derive the estimated QoS metric of candidate network configurations including path and queue configurations. Then the valid candidate configurations generated from the analysis engine will be fed into the decision engine to achieve the system objective defined by network operator with AI algorithm, e.g., RL, DL or FL. Figure 3 shows the intelligent management framework for deterministic networks.

Figure 3. Intelligent Management Framework for Deterministic Networks

As a part of 6G-SANDBOX Library, deterministic networking will enable a TSN testbed (wired or wireless configuration) with the following features:

- TSN devices available on the testbed for wired and wireless configuration
- Show the traffic statistics of Ethernet ports of TSN bridges.
- Management and configuration of the main TSN features through SNMPv3, SSH, Netconf, HTTPS (*Interoperability test pending) of TSN bridges:
 - IEEE 802.1AS - Timing and Synchronization
 - IEEE 802.1Qbv - Enhancements for Scheduled Traffic
 - IEEE 802.1Qav - Forwarding and Queuing Enhancements for Time-Sensitive Streams
 - IEEE 802.1Qcc – Enhancements for Stream Reservation Protocol
 - IEEE 802.1Qci* – Per-Stream Filtering and Policing
 - IEEE 802.1CB* – Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability
 - IEEE 802.1Qbu* & IEEE 802.3br* – Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability

- Intelligent network management framework
 - Network monitoring
 - Network analysis
 - Network control and configuration
 - Network optimization

2.5 DETERMINISTIC NETWORKING - NETWORK PROGRAMMING WITH P4

2.5.1 CONCEPT AND SIGNIFICANCE

Programming Protocol-independent Packet Processors (P4) is the most widely used programming language for network devices, specifically tailored for programming the data plane. It originated from a research paper in 2014 [8] and is now being developed and standardized by the P4 Language Consortium, a non-profit organization organized by the Open Networking Foundation (ONF) [9]. This standardization allows for compatibility with numerous software and hardware platforms in today's networking ecosystem.

P4 is in the realm of Next Generation – Software Defined Networking (NG-SDN), which represents an evolutionary step beyond Software Defined Networks (SDN). A comparison between SDN and NG-SDN networks is depicted in Figure 4. SDN networks are known for their ability to eliminate the rigidity found in traditional networks by separating the control plane and the data plane, and by enabling user programmability of the control plane. SDN networks can be seen as networks with a Bottom-Up design, where the hardware chip of the network element has a fixed set of units, and higher-level software is used to program functions that utilize these fixed units.

On the other hand, NG-SDN networks provide the capability to program both the control plane and the data plane of network elements, while SDN networks only allow programming of the control plane. This inherent difference makes NG-SDN networks significantly more efficient. Consequently, NG-SDN networks are designed with a Top-Down approach, which involves initially conceptualizing high-level functionality and then directly programming elementary functions into the chip.

Figure 4: NG-SDN networks

Programming both the control and data plane of a network element results in complete control and flexibility over the processing of network packets. In other words, it allows users to add, modify, or remove algorithms, protocols, and functions in a completely customizable and efficient manner. All these advantages make programming a network element using an NG-SDN approach an optimal tool for developing P4 modules in the transport network of the Malaga platform for 6G-SANDBOX. Specifically, two P4 modules are being developed: telemetry modules and a UPF-P4 module.

Starting with the telemetry module, it plays a pivotal role in a 5G/6G network by enabling real-time monitoring and data collection from network devices and infrastructure. The P4 language enables efficient and precise data collection through programming the data plane, enabling efficient, real-time, and flexible network monitoring. Additionally, the P4 consortium has developed a standardized specification for Network In-band Telemetry (INT) [10], enhancing compatibility and facilitating its implementation.

INT is a framework designed to enable the collection and reporting of network state solely through the data plane. This approach eliminates the need for control plane intervention in gathering and delivering network state data. In the INT architectural model, packets can carry special header fields interpreted as 'telemetry instructions' by network devices. INT sources, such as applications, end-host networking stacks, and network components, embed these instructions within data packets, clone copies of data packets, or use special probe packets to convey network state. Alternatively, the instructions can be programmed in the network's data plane to match specific network flows and execute the instructions accordingly.

These instructions tell an INT-capable device what state to collect. The collected network state information can either be directly exported by the data plane to the telemetry monitoring system or can be encapsulated within the packet as it traverses the network. In cases where the information is encapsulated within the packets, INT traffic sinks retrieved and, if desired, reports the collected results of these instructions. This empowers traffic sinks to monitor the specific data plane state that the packets effectively 'observed' during their journey through the network.

Thanks to this P4 telemetry, INT modules have been developed and will be deployed throughout the network of the Málaga platform for 6G-SANDBOX to capture various metrics, including latency, hop count, and more. The telemetry information collected by these INT modules will be used by network components to maintain the expected end-to-end quality in deterministic networks. For instance, latency data will allow network devices to quickly detect and react to any performance degradation, ensuring that the strict latency requirements of delay-sensitive applications are met. Furthermore, hop count metrics will help optimize packet forwarding paths to minimize the number of intermediate nodes, further reducing latency and improving overall network reliability.

On the other hand, the UPF is the most crucial module in the data plane of a 5G network, serving as a gateway between the RAN access network and external data networks (PDNs). It is responsible for a multitude of functionalities related to user data traffic, including packet forwarding and routing between RAN and PDN, routing mobile device traffic as they switch between base stations, storing inactive device traffic, enforcing rules to ensure specific QoS requirements, and reporting user data traffic statistics for subsequent billing by the CP.

By employing an NG-SDN design with P4, it becomes possible to fully program a 5G UPF module based on 3GPP technical specifications. Leveraging the advantages of NG-SDN and P4, this results in a high-performance UPF-P4 module that is efficient, entirely flexible, and real-time controllable.

The UPF-P4 module in 6G-SANDBOX serves as a valuable tool in enhancing the transport network of the Malaga infrastructure, enabling the attainment of the requisite features for deterministic communications. These features consist of ensuring low latency, delivering quality of service, efficient traffic management, traffic prioritization, and reliability.

2.5.2 ROLE IN 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

The goal is to develop two P4 modules for the Malaga platform's infrastructure: a telemetry module based on the standardized specification of the P4 consortium and a UPF-P4 module adhering to the technical specifications outlined by 3GPP.

As a part of 6G-SANDBOX Library, P4 telemetry will enable the following features:

- Enhanced ability to detect and diagnose issues affecting user traffic, leading to faster problem resolution and a better overall user experience.
- Monitoring and generation of numerous packet-level, user flow, or interface metrics. These metrics include packet ingress and egress interfaces, internal latency, and timestamping for ingress and egress.
- Generation of reports of the measurements stored in InfluxDB.
- Visualization of metrics with Grafana.

As a part of 6G-SANDBOX Library, the UPF module will enable the following features:

- Complete implementation of a UPF module based on 3GPP Release 16. This includes two parts: the UPF functionality and a controller that translates PFCP messages from the SMF module of a 5G network's control plane into P4 control messages to insert rules into the P4 tables.
- Improved scalability and performance of user plane processing, ensuring a seamless and responsive user experience even as traffic demands grow.
- Enhanced support for network slicing and Quality of Service (QoS) differentiation, enabling users to benefit from tailored service levels based on their specific requirements.

2.6 EXTENDED REALITY (XR)

2.6.1 CONCEPT AND SIGNIFICANCE

The “Extended Reality” concept (XR) [13] encompasses applications that provide an experience to end users capable of extending or even fully replacing what their human senses get from the surrounding world. Assisted by specialized devices (Head Mounted Displays, haptic gloves, or vests, etc.) users get an enriched version of reality (augmented reality) or a completely new environment, either generated by a computer (virtual reality) or captured from a remote location (telepresence) [14].

The main technologies required for implementing XR applications [15] and their linkage with the network are:

- **Head Mounted Displays** (VR goggles, AR goggles), which sense the position and pose of the user in space and project images directly in the eyes of the user. They also include audio, with the ability to simulate spatial feeling. Although in most cases these devices are self-contained, in some scenarios part of their functionality may be offloaded to the network, to reduce the HMD size or increase the battery lifetime.
- **Haptic devices:** gloves, sleeves, vests, etc. with different types of actuators that produce tactile sensations in users wearing them. These devices may be controlled by the HMD, from a local computer or directly from the network. For the relevance in this project, they are described in detail in the next subsection.
- **Immersive media:** when the XR application is based on real scenarios captured from the physical world we need efficient ways of performing that capture. This includes wide angle cameras, ideally covering 360 degrees (immersive video) or, beyond that, a volumetric capture setup capable of capturing a whole area that enables six degrees of freedom at rendering side. This capture typically generates a huge amount of data that must be delivered in real time through the network.
- **Computer models** (virtual scenarios and objects for augmentation). The rendering in real time of scenes from these models may be done locally in a standalone HMD, in a computer connected to it (tethered HMD), remotely in the cloud (cloud rendering), or a combination of them (distributed rendering, or “split rendering”). All rendering options that include a remote component pose strong requirements on the network for sending bulky video frames with a very low latency, because the rendering needs to quickly follow the physical movements of the user's head and body.
- **Analytics:** the mediation provided by XR applications between the real world and the human senses may be leveraged to provide additional features based on a semantic analysis of the captured data. This

is typically done in servers in the network, through the processing by AI algorithms of the video and audio streams. This process may include classification (identifying objects and actions), segmentation (cutting off objects from the scene) and generation (creation of new objects or modifications of existing ones).

The relevance of XR applications for the 5G/6G network [16] comes from their high demand for resources. Firstly, immersive media requires a very high data rate on capture and transmission, spanning from tens or hundreds of Mbps to several Gbps for a single captured location. Additionally, the reliability of the transmission of this data must be exceptionally high to keep the illusion of presence, that is, the credibility for the brain of the artificial scene which is being composed through the devices that the end user is wearing. Even minimal errors in the transmission produce artifacts in video and audio that spoil the experience revealing that it is not as real as it should appear. Finally, latency of XR transmission is equally important: communication-oriented applications require that the round trip of communication exchange is fast enough. But the highest demand in this aspect, comes from edge processing requirements: rendering must follow accurately the physical moves of end users (when you turn your head to the right the scene needs to be rendered from that perspective almost instantly), and when rendering is done remotely this requires round trips below a frame time (20-40 ms).

Haptic Devices

Haptic devices are wearable systems with different types of actuators that produce tactile sensations in users wearing them. These devices may be controlled by the HMD, from a local computer or directly from the network.

Figure 5. Haptic Vest devices

OWO is a haptic system shown in Figure 5 that allows users to feel real physical sensations in real time by using pulse trains to stimulate the muscle and, thanks to its algorithm, modify up to nine of the train pulse's parameters to recreate a sensation. The system is composed of two elements: the OWO Skin and the Device.

The OWO Skin is a vest with 20 electrodes to cover all the upper part muscles (pectorals, biceps, abdominals, dorsal muscles, and lumbar muscles). These electrodes must be in direct contact with the user's bare skin to feel the sensations properly, avoiding being over any kind of fabric. On the right side, there is a pocket where the user must plug the Device into the vest.

The Device is responsible for generating the sensations and applying them to the vest. It is controlled by a mobile application available for PC, iOS and Android. Users must have an account to use the OWO system. With an account, users can adjust their own levels of intensity when feeling sensations, creating a comfortable and unique experience.

2.6.2 ROLE IN 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

The characteristics of XR traffic do not fully fit into any of the existing models (eMBB, URLLC or mMTC). The peculiarities of these applications have been analyzed in 3GPP [17] from 2016 (SA, SA4), releases 17 and 18 already consider it. The focus so far has been on power saving, scale and service performance. Multiple XR use cases have been identified, classified in three groups: VR, AR and cloud gaming. Main KPIs considered in them are capacity (based on satisfaction level) and power consumption. These are some sample use cases:

- Viewport dependent VR: remote rendering of a VR scene in which only the part visible to the HMD (depending on the orientation) is generated and sent.
- Augmented Reality functionality assisted from the network. In particular, the positioning algorithms based on SLAM (Simultaneous Location and Mapping) can be offloaded partially to a server nearby.
- Split rendering, when the rendering process is distributed across different devices in the delivery chain, from the cloud to the end device.

Our approach with respect to XR within 6G-SANDBOX is focused on guaranteeing resources from the network for the execution of XR applications with enough quality. To do that we plan to build a new network component which will be XR aware, and which will facilitate that quality guarantee to application developers. These are the main requirements that we consider for this module:

- The XR extension module will behave as intermediation between the application and the internals of the 5G/6G networks. This way, users of this module at application level (XR) will not need to be aware of the complexities of the network, or the existing implementation.
- The API will be offered as a library, following the Network as Code paradigm, to facilitate the adoption by typical XR application developers. Network as Code is a concept of extreme simplification of network capabilities to enable applications to dynamically change the network to optimize performance and user experience. It enables the building of new business and technology frameworks, focusing on distributed service chains and facilitating the inclusion of developers and vertical technology partners for value creation. Using an SDK, in this case as a Python class, that provides access to the NaC REST API, developers are given comprehensive access to network capabilities.
- The implementation of the quality guarantees in this module will use any tools that the network offers, such as application aware schedulers, PDU IDs, uplink enhancements, carrier aggregation, new MIMO models, etc. Both standards-based tools and any proprietary mechanisms available in the 6G-SANDBOX testbed may be used by the XR extension module.
- KPIs will be measured in the resulting scenario for the available use cases. At least a use case related to immersive telepresence will be implemented, although it is also expected that third party applications may also be integrated, possibly as part of the Open Calls.

Figure 6 describes the high level of the proposed XR extension architecture:

Figure 6: High level of the proposed XR extension architecture

Note that as of today no HMD in the market supports 5G or in general mobile connections natively. They are typically connected via WiFi to a nearby router or, in tethered HMD cases, to a fiber connection through an Ethernet from the computer to which the HMD is connected.

The sample use case which will be integrated with this architecture will be the immersive communication application developed by Nokia (“The Owl”) with the addition of haptic functionality provided by Owo. This use case features most of the described XR high requirements: bidirectional real time communication, high bandwidth, strong uplink, low end-to-end delay, multi-modal streams (video, audio, haptics, pose, data) and even edge processing.

Figure 7. Sensations Creator software

Regarding haptic devices, OWO has a Development Software shown in Figure 7 that allows the creation of sensations regulating the following nine parameters:

- Frequency: Adapts the frequency of the pulse, spanning from 1 to 100 Hertz

- Intensity: Defines the intensity of the pulse, from 0 to 80.
- Duration: Specifies the timeframe, 100 a 400 μ s
- Fade In: Starts the sensation with a ramp up entry signal.
- Fade Out: Starts the sensation with a ramp down exit signal.
- Exit Time: Determines the time between two signal inputs.
- Channel: Allows the selection of the muscle to which the sensation is sent. It might be more than one.
- Interphase: Specifies the time between the positive and negative sections of the signal.

The integration of each of the parameters aforementioned in a specific period of time is called microsensation. A full sensation can be composed of either one or more microsensations.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Sensations Creator software's microsensations

Figures 8 a and 8b show a set of microsensations. Notice that the first one has a Fade In and is sent to the arm, whereas the second one has a small exit time and is sent to a set of different muscles.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF TECHNOLOGY ENABLERS IN 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

3.1 O-RAN IMPLEMENTATION

The IS-Wireless Liquid RAN solution can be deployed as O-DU, O-CU or combined O-DU/O-CU in a few different ways, for example with Docker Compose, Docker Swarm, or Kubernetes. As mentioned in this document, the basic deployment is described as CNF on a Docker container with Docker Compose. In the case of single machine deployment (combined O-DU/O-CU), the user has one *.yaml file for entity management and network configuration is extremely easy. In the case of several machines (O-DU, O-CU or separate O-CU-CP and O-CU-UP), the user has to configure several * .yaml files and properly configure the networks. Figure 9 shows the general deployment of O-RAN architecture.

Figure 9. General deployment of O-RAN architecture

The novelty of this O-RAN implementation at the UMA platform can be summarized as:

- Implementation of the xApp Prediction Agent and Possibility to Import/Modify AI/ML Model (LSTM): This feature represents a significant advancement by incorporating predictive analytics directly into the RAN. By leveraging Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models—a form of recurrent neural network (RNN) known for its ability to remember information for long periods—the xApp Prediction Agent can forecast network conditions, user behavior, and potential congestion. The ability to import and modify these AI/ML models ensures that the system remains adaptable and can evolve with emerging technologies and requirements.
- xApp Placement Agent and Possibility to Import/Modify AI/ML Model (RL): This element introduces the use of Reinforcement Learning (RL) to optimize the placement of xApps within the network. RL algorithms learn by interacting with their environment, making decisions that maximize some notion of cumulative reward. This capability means that the xApp Placement Agent can continuously improve its decision-making process regarding where and when (e.g., CU-UP) to deploy xApps for optimal network performance and resource utilization.
- Extension of the xApp KPM with New Metric for CSI (Required by Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS)): Enhancing the Key Performance Metrics (KPM) xApp to include new metrics specifically for Channel State Information (CSI) required by JCAS is a forward-looking innovation. This extension acknowledges the growing importance of RIS in optimizing signal propagation and network coverage, particularly for future-proofing networks and supporting emerging use cases that require highly adaptable network environments.
- Modify Scaling Feature to Utilize “ONE Service” to Trigger Scaling: This modification introduces a more dynamic and responsive scaling mechanism for xApps, leveraging the "ONE Service" for triggering scaling actions. This approach potentially allows for more granular and situation-aware scaling of network functions, improving resource efficiency and responsiveness to sudden changes in network demand.

- Provide Extension to Allow xApp to Store KPMs into DB (Influx): By enabling xApps to store Key Performance Metrics directly into a time-series database like InfluxDB, this feature enhances the capacity for detailed performance analysis and long-term data retention. This capability is crucial for monitoring network health, planning capacity, and analyzing trends over time.
- Demonstrate “Hello World” xApp and Integration with the 6G-SANDBOX Platform (TNLCM, etc.): Offering a "Hello World" xApp, alongside integration with the 6G-SANDBOX platform, serves as an essential tool for developers and engineers to get started with xApp development and testing in a simulated environment. This foundation is vital for encouraging innovation, experimentation, and the broader adoption of O-RAN principles.

3.1.1 NETWORK COMPONENTS

The IS-Wireless Liquid RAN software can be deployed on different infrastructures (computers, servers, cloud). Hardware requirements depend on the network configuration and performance of the processor used. For example, the minimum requirements of HW requirements for single cell (Channel bandwidth 40 MHz, MIMO 2 by 2, Max 256 QAM) in DL can be recommended as in Table 1.

Table 1. An example of HW Requirements for single cell

Bandwidth	CNF	Processor (Example)	vCPU	Memory	Storage
40 MHz	O-DU only	PC: minimum 9 th Gen Intel x64 core i7 9700K Server: minimum xeon gen2	10	16 G	100 GB + logs
40 MHz	O-CU only	PC: minimum 9 th Gen Intel x64 core i7 9700K Server: minimum xeon gen2	6	16 G	100 GB + logs
40 MHz	O-DU/O-CU	PC: minimum 9 th Gen Intel x64 core i7 9700K Server: minimum xeon gen2	16	32G	200 GB + logs

To ensure the smooth deployment of the IS-Wireless Liquid RAN solution, it's critical to properly prepare the software environment across several key areas. Firstly, the BIOS should be configured to Low Latency/Real-Time Mode, and if a low-latency profile is available within the BIOS setup utility, it should be selected to optimize latency based on the system vendor's recommendations. The operating system must meet real-time requirements for the Radio Unit (RU), necessitating adjustments to both the OS and its kernel to handle real-time processing demands efficiently. Virtualization support is provided through Docker, requiring Docker version 20.10.8 or newer and Docker Compose version 1.29.2 or newer to be installed. Additionally, the solution is compatible with processor architectures including x86 and AMD. Ensuring these software environment prerequisites are met is essential for the successful implementation and performance of the IS-Wireless Liquid RAN solution.

3.1.2 NETWORK DESCRIPTION

Figure 10. Liquid RAN testbed design

The deployed Liquid RAN in the UMA testbed depicted in Figure 10 consists of O-DU, O-CU, Near-RT RIC and the relevant xApp(s). O-DU, O-CU, Near-RT RIC and xApp are deployed as containers within a single server. While O-DU, O-CU, Near-RT RIC are interconnected with standard interfaces (F1 and E2), xApp is attached to RIC via a proprietary interface. Liquid RAN ecosystem is connected to the external components in the following way:

- O-DU communicates with RU over the Fronthaul interface. In this deployment the Benetel 550 indoor unit is used as RU.
- O-CU communicates with 5G Core Network (5GC) over standard defined N2/N3 interfaces.
- xApp includes an external interface incorporating OpenAPI which allows standard means to access RAN related metrics.

To deploy LiquidRAN a Docker Compose is used. In this case one Docker Compose YAML descriptor file is needed to start the system.

The network key performance matrices (KPM) xApp GUI are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. KPM xApp GUI

The network key performance metrics are mentioned as follows:

- RRC.ConnMean - Number of Connected UEs
- RRU.PrbTotDI - DL Total PRB Usage on DL [%]
- RRU.PrbTotUI - UL Total PRB Usage on UL [%]
- RRU.PrbAvailDI - DL Available PRBs (number, not %), (total 106 is max for 40MHz, on the screenshots we could see the upper range 90 for DL and 20 for UL)
- RRU.PrbAvailUI - DL Available PRBs (number, not %)

- TB.TotNbrDL.X - Total number of DL TBs per second. Number of radio transmissions per second. Number of TTIs (DL) per second (including transmission and retransmission). In 5G there are 2000 TTIs per second(1=0.5ms), so for example there cannot be more than 2000 on the charts.
- TB.TotNbrUL.X - Total number of UL TBs per second. Number of radio transmissions per second. Number of TTIs (UL) per second (including transmission and retransmission). In 5G there are 2000 TTIs per second(1=0.5ms), so for example there cannot be more than 2000 on the charts. We have less for UL because of the number of the UL slots.
- TB.ErrTolNbrDL.X - TTIs with negative HARQ, per second, for DL
- TB.ErrTolNbrUL.X - TTIs with negative HARQ, per second, for DL
- DRB.UETpDI - Average DL Data Rate per UE in Kbits/second
- DRB.UETpUI - Average UL Data Rate per UE in Kbits/second

3.1.3 6G LIBRARY OBJECT

This section will present the description of the O-RAN 6G Library Object. It includes two different Objects, such as openran_CUDU and openran_RIC.

3.1.3.1 OPENRAN_CUDU

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network? Yes
- Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? Yes
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace?
 - Yes (Private)
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Yes
 - Which networks?
 - INTERNET
- Is this object going to be available for all sites?
 - No (Only UMA)
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
- Yes
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?
 - two

Object information

Component Name: openran_CUDU

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	open5gs, openran_RIC, openran_RU (TMP)
Short Desc	Deployment of OpenRAN as Docker Image.
Long Desc	Simple description of IS-Wireless OpenRAN solution: https://www.is-wireless.com/networks/software/
Hypervisors	[one]
Sites	[uma]

Public Object Input Parameters:

Public variables are those whose value can be modified from the TNLCM portal.

Required input parameters add information that can't be set with defaults, like dependencies with other deployed components.

Variable types are currently int, str, intlist and strlist.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required When
RAN_band_indicator	The IE FreqBandIndicatorNR is used to convey an NR frequency band number as defined in TS 38.101-1 and TS 38.101-2.	int	78	(1..1024)	true
RAN_pointa_arfcn_dl	Absolute frequency position of the reference resource block (Common RB 0). Its lowest subcarrier is also known as Point A (see TS 38.211, clause 4.4.4.2).	int	646062	(0..maxNARFCN)	true
RAN_pointa_arfcn_ul	Absolute frequency position of the reference resource block (Common RB 0). Its lowest subcarrier is also known as Point A (see TS 38.211 [16], clause 4.4.4.2).	int	646062	(0..maxNARFCN)	true
RAN_gscn	Range depends on NR operating band, see Table 5.4.3.3-1: Applicable SS raster entries per operating band in 3GPP #38.101-1.	int	7982	[]	true
RAN_ssb_arfcn	Frequency referring to the position of resource element RE=#0 (subcarrier #0) of resource block RB#10 of the SS block. Value ARFCN, see ARFCN-ValueNR 3GPP #38.331.	int	646368	(0..maxNARFCN)	true

RAN_k_ssb	k_SSB corresponds to the gap between SC 0 of SS/PBCH block and Common Resource Block (N_SSB_CRB). N_SSB_CRB is obtained from the higher-layer parameter OffsetToPointA. k_SSB value is obtained from the MIB parameter ssb-SubcarrierOffset. From 3GPP #38.211 7.4.2.3.2	int	18	(x..x)	true
RAN_offsetToPointA	Represents the offset to Point A as defined in TS 38.211 [16], clause 4.4.4.2.	int	4	(0..2199)	true
RAN_config_idx	Index see Index in Table 13-1 and Table 13-4 in 3GPP #38.213	int	7	(0..15)	true
RAN_ric_enable	O-DU Near-Real Time RIC interface status.	str	true	true/false	true
CONFIG	#Configuration File	str	tdd_7ds 2u_40m hz_30ks cs_MIM O2x2	F1_fdd_10mhz_15k scs_SISO F1_fdd_20mhz_15k scs_MIMO2x2 F1_fdd_20mhz_15k scs_SISO F1_fdd_5mhz_15ksc s_SISO F1_tdd_3ds1u_10m hz_30kscs_MIMO2x 2 F1_tdd_3ds1u_10m hz_30kscs_SISO F1_tdd_3ds1u_20m hz_30kscs_MIMO2x 2 F1_tdd_3ds1u_20m hz_30kscs_SISO F1_tdd_3ds1u_30m hz_30kscs_SISO F1_tdd_3ds1u_40m hz_30kscs_SISO F1_tdd_3ds1u_40m hz_30kscs_MIMO2x 2	true

				F1_tdd_3ds1u_100 mhz_30kscs_MIMO 2x2 F1_tdd_7ds2u_10m hz_30kscs_MIMO2x 2 F1_tdd_7ds2u_10m hz_30kscs_SISO F1_tdd_7ds2u_20m hz_30kscs_MIMO2x 2 F1_tdd_7ds2u_20m hz_30kscs_SISO F1_tdd_7ds2u_30m hz_30kscs_SISO F1_tdd_7ds2u_40m hz_30kscs_MIMO2x 2 F1_tdd_7ds2u_40m hz_30kscs_SISO F1_tdd_7ds2u_100 mhz_30kscs_MIMO 2x2	
L1H_maxNumPdschLayers	Maximum number of PDSCH layers supported in this release (errors out if not fulfilled by L2). Use 2 while testing MIMO 2x2.	int	2		true
L1H_maxNumPuschLayers	MIMO UL configuration. Maximum number of PUSCH layers supported in this release (errors out if not fulfilled by L2). Only value 1 is supported.	int	1		true
L1H_maxNumDlFrontalPrbs	Maximum number of Physical Resource Blocks on downlink. Parameter shall be used only for Benetel RAN550/RAN650 CAT-B v0.8.0 setup. Value 144 shall be used only for 100 MHz bandwidth. Value 106 shall be used only for 40 MHz bandwidth.	int	106	144 , 106	true

ISW_GLOBAL_LOG_LEVEL	Log level	str	EMERG	LOG, EMERG, DEBUG	true
SDRAN_DEBUG	While EMERG should be 0, while DEBUG should be 1	int	0		true
RAN_pci_val	physCellId see 3GPP #38.331. The PhysCellId identifies the physical cell identity (PCI).	int	5	(0..1007)	true
RAN_mcc_val (optional)	Mobile Country Code (MCC) consisting of three digits. The MCC identifies uniquely the country of domicile of the mobile subscriber (see TS 23.003).	int	999		false
RAN_mnc_val (optional)	Mobile Network Code (MNC) consisting of two or three digits for mobile subscriber. The length of the MNC (two or three digits) depends on the value of the MCC. A mixture of two and three digit MNC codes within a single MCC area is not recommended and is outside the scope of this specification. (see TS 23.003)	int	98		false
RAN_gnb_id	Global gNB ID see #38.413. This IE is used to globally identify a gNB (see TS 38.300 [8]). Global gNB ID Equal to the leftmost bits of the NR Cell Identity IE contained in the NR CGI IE of each cell served by the gNB.	str	00E0001	BIT STRING (SIZE(22..32))	true
RAN_cell_id	Cell identity. Value in this file is decimal, but it is encoded hexadecimal.	int	12	Range: from 0 up to 16383 (maximum value depends on gNB ID)	false
RAN_tac	Tracking Area Code (TAC) see 3GPP TS	int	1		false

	29.571 / 3GPP TS 38.413 Parameter identifying a tracking area code, in decimal representation.				
RAN_root_sequence_idx	prach-RootSequenceIndex l139 see 3GPP #38.331 PRACH root sequence index (see TS 38.211 [16], clause 6.3.3.1).	int	10	INTEGER (0..137)	true
RAN_neighborhood	RAN_neighborhood - Configuration of neighbourhood cells for handover purposes. Configure PCI, Global gNB ID, MCC, MNC and TAC of the neighbourhood cells for the 5G SA handover purposes.	str	{\ "pci\ ": 88, \ "global_id\ ": \ "0x00F00\ ", \ "mcc\ ": 1, \ "mnc\ ": 1, \ "mnc_eu\ ": 1, \ "tac\ ": 1 }		true
RAN_rrm_policy_list	RAN_rrm_policy_list is an array of RRM Policies, where one policy, which contains rrmPolicyMaxRatio, rrmPolicyMinRatio, rrmPolicyDedicatedRatio, corresponds to one slice. rrmPolicyMaxRatio – This parameter determines the maximum ratio (in percentage) of the total resources that an RRM Policy can use in the slicing window. If this value is set to 80 (for example) then it will only allow the slice configured to utilise up to 80% of the total resources even if it is the only slice that is transmitting. The sum of all rrmPolicyMaxRatio that is configured for all RRM Policies can total to more than 100.	str	{\ "rrmPolicyMaxRatio\ ": 100, \ "rrmPolicyMinRatio\ ": 20, \ "rrmPolicyDedicatedRatio\ ": 0, \ "slices\ ": [{ \ "sst\ ": 1, \ "sd\ ":- 1}], \ "rrmPolicyMaxRatio\ ": 100, \ "rrmPolicyMinRatio\ ": 80, \ "rrmPolicyDedicatedRatio\ ": 0, \ "slices\ ": [{ \ "sst\ ": 2, \ "sd\ ":- 1}] }		false

	<p>rrmPolicyMinRatio – This parameter determines the minimum ratio (in percentage) of the total resources that an RRM Policy can use in the slicing window. This will determine the minimum percentage allocated for the configured slice during times wherein multiple slices are transmitting. In the example above wherein one RRM Policy is configured with rrmPolicyMinRatio = 80 and the other with rrmPolicyMinRatio = 20, then the total resources will be split in those ratios when both configured slices are transmitting. The sum of all rrmPolicyMinRatio that is configured for all RRM Policies CANNOT exceed 100.</p> <p>rrmPolicyDedicatedRatio – This parameter determines the ratio (in percentage) of resources that are allocated for an RRM Policy regardless of whether or not these resources are utilised in the slicing window. If this was set to rrmDedicatedRatio = 20 for an RRM Policy then the total resources that can be used by all the other RRM Policies cannot exceed 80 percent regardless if the slices under that specific RRM Policy are using these dedicated resources or not.</p>				
--	---	--	--	--	--

RAN_pdsch_mcs_table	<p>RAN_pdsch_mcs_table determines the value of the mcs-Table RRC IE that is sent to the UE.</p> <p>A value of -1 means mcs-Table is not sent and UE will use the default MCS index table 1 (Table 5.1.3.1-1 3GPP 38.214). This means UE will use up to 64QAM only.</p> <p>A value of 0 corresponds to sending "qam256" as mcs-Table to the UE and that UE will use MCS index table 2 (Table 5.1.3.1-2 3GPP 38.214). This means UE will use up to 256QAM modulation.</p>	int	-1		false
RAN_cqi_table	<p>RAN_cqi_table determines the value of cqi-Table RRC IE that is sent to the UE.</p> <p>A value of "table1" means sending table1 as cqi-Table and UE will use CQI Table 1 (Table 5.2.2.1-2 3GPP 38.214) when reporting CQI. This should be used when using only up to 64QAM modulation.</p> <p>A value of "table2" means sending table1 as cqi-Table and UE will use CQI Table 2 (Table 5.2.2.1-3 3GPP 38.214) when reporting CQI. This should be used when using up to 256QAM modulation.</p>	str	\"table1 \"	\"table1\", \"table2\"	false
RAN_dl_mcs_table	<p>RAN_dl_mcs_table determines which MCS Table will be used in DU as specified in 5.1.3.1 3GPP 38.214 : A value of 1 corresponds to Table 5.1.3.1-1: MCS index table 1 for PDSCH. This allows for up to 64QAM</p>	int	1	1, 2	false

	modulation. A value of 2 corresponds to Table 5.1.3.1-2: MCS index table 2 for PDSCH. This allows for up to 256QAM modulation.				
RAN_ss_PBCH_Block Power	<p>#ss-PBCH-BlockPower see 3GPP #38.331 36 Average EPRE of the resources elements that carry secondary synchronisation signals in dBm that the NW used for SSB transmission, see TS 38.213 [13], clause 7. Calculation: $ssPBCHBlockPower = PRU + GRU - 10 \log(12 * carrierBandwidth)$ [dBm] Where the PRU is the transmission power of the Radio Unit in dBm, GRU is the antenna gain of the radio unit in dBi and carrierBandwidth is the number of DL PRBs transmitted in SIB1</p>	int	-24	(-60..50)	true
RAN_tx_power	Internal RAN parameter which is forwarded to the UL1. Need to be set to the same value as ss-PBCH-BlockPower (see parameter above)	int	-24	(-60..50)	true
RAN_p0_NominalWithGrant	P0 value for PUSCH with grant (except msg3). Value in dBm. Only even values (step size 2) allowed (see TS 38.213, clause 7.1) This field is cell specific	int	-78	(-202..24)	true
RAN_p0_nominal	Power control parameter P0 for PUCCH transmissions. Value in dBm. Only even values (step size 2) allowed (see TS 38.213, clause 7.2).	float	-80	(-202..24)	true

RAN_preambleReceivedTargetPower	The target power level at the network receiver side (see TS 38.213, clause 7.4, TS 38.321, clauses 5.1.2, 5.1.3).	int	-60	(-202..-60) Only multiples of 2 dBm may be chosen (e.g. -202, -200, -198, ...).	true
RAN_p_max	The IE P-Max is used to limit the UE's uplink transmission power on a carrier frequency, in TS 38.101-1 and is used to calculate the parameter Pcompensation defined in TS 38.304.	int	33	(-30..33)	true
RAN_alpha	PUSCH-PowerControl Information element alpha value for PUSCH with grant (except msg3) (see TS 38.213, clause 7.1). The IE Alpha defines possible values of the pathloss compensation coefficient for uplink power control.	int	7	alpha0 = 0, alpha04 = 1, alpha05 = 2, alpha06 = 3, alpha07 = 4, alpha08 = 5, alpha09 = 6, #alpha1 = 7	true
RAN_qfi_AM	Optional parameters, which allow to change the AM or UM QFI profile of any configuration template. Examples: Switch QFI 7 and QFI 9 to AM and update parameters (if any)	str	7,9		false
RAN_qfi_UM	Switch QFI 69 to UM and update parameters (if any)	int	69		false
RAN_rlcAM_sn_FieldLength	Optionally all parameters used in rlc_config {} section of the modified QFI profile can be configured from env with RAN_rlcAM_<parameter> or RAN_rlcUM_<parameter>. RLC AM parameters for DRB and default values:	int	1		false

	AM SN field size in bits - see 3GPP TS 38.331				
RAN_rlcAM_t_PollRetransmit	Timer used by the transmitting side of an AM RLC entity in order to retransmit a poll - see 3GPP TS 38.331	int	8		false
RAN_rlcAM_pollPDU	Used by the transmitting side of each AM RLC entity to trigger a poll for every pollPDU PDUs - see 3GPP TS 38.331	int	23		false
RAN_rlcAM_pollByte	Used by the transmitting side of each AM RLC entity to trigger a poll for every pollByte bytes - see 3GPP TS 38.331	int	43		false
RAN_rlcAM_maxRetxThreshold	Used by the transmitting side of each AM RLC entity to limit the number of retransmissions of an AMD PDU - see 3GPP TS 38.331	int	5		false
RAN_rlcAM_t_Reassembly	Timer used by the receiving side of an AM RLC entity in order to monitor waiting time for AMD PDU - see 3GPP TS 38.331	int	7		false
RAN_rlcAM_t_StatusProhibit	Timer used by the receiving side of an AM RLC entity in order to prohibit transmission of a STATUS PDU - see 3GPP TS 38.331	int	0		false
RAN_rlcUM_sn_FieldLength	RLC UM parameters for DRB and default values: UM SN field size in bits - see 3GPP TS 38.331	int	0		false
RAN_rlcUM_t_Reassembly	#Timer used by the receiving side of an AM RLC entity in order to monitor waiting time for UMD PDU - see 3GPP TS 38.331	int	8		false

ISW_SPLIT_LOGS	#Log dump to file configuration	str	yes		true
ISW_SPLIT_LOGS_MEGABYTES	#Log dump to file configuration	int	1024		true
ISW_SPLIT_LOGS_SUFFIX	#Log dump to file configuration	str	_ran550_iswlog		true
ISW_SPLIT_LOGS_DELETE_OLDER	#Log dump to file configuration	int	3		true

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value
STACK_TYPE	#Stack type: 4G/5G	str	5g
RU_IP	#O-RU IP. IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx).	str	10.10.2.100
RAN_ric_ip	Near-Real Time RIC IP. Hostname (string) or IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx).	str	172.27.2.1
RAN_ric_port	Near-Real Time RIC port. Default is 37464 (also default for Wireshark).	int	1234
ISW_CPU_CORES_PHY	example CPU core isolation for UL1 (PHY) and L2 (RAN)	str	"4,28,6,30,8,32,10,34"
ISW_CPU_CORES_RAN	example CPU core isolation for UL1 (PHY) and L2 (RAN)	str	"12,36,14,38,16,40"
L1H_bbuFronhaulServerMode	UL1 fronthaul server mode (0 for UDP with send checksum on, 1 for UDP with send checksum off, otherwise undefined).	int	1
L1H_bbuFronhaulServerAddr	UL1 interface IP. UL1 is listening for LL1 requests on this IP. Format: "\xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx\ NOTE: IP is filled in according to the example in the user manual	str	"\10.10.2.10\ "
L1H_maxPuschModOrder	#Maximum PUSCH modulation order supported in this release (errors out if not fulfilled by L2) #1 - BPSK #2 - QPSK #4 - 16QAM #6 - 64QAM #8 - 256QAM	int	6

L1H_targetRecvDelay_us	Target delay [us] for uplink with respect to downlink, measured by Backend. RU dependent. Value 2500 shall be used only for the USRP/CableFree setup. Value 1479 shall be used only for the Benetel RAN550/RAN650 CAT-B v0.8.0 setup.	int	1479
L1H_otherLayerKeepaliveTimer_ms	UL1 parameter Mandatory for all Benetel RU deployments	int	30
L1H_timingOffsetThreshold_nsec	Mandatory only for Benetel RU deployments	int	10000
L1H_rruFronthaulClientAddr	RU fronthaul client IP (Only for Benetel RU deployments)	str	"10.10.0.100"
L1H_rruFronthaulClientPort	RU fronthaul client port (Only for Benetel RU deployments)	int	44000
L1H_fronthaulStreamingDelay_us	Delay [us] between completed handshake and start of the transmission (Only for Benetel RU deployments)	int	7000
HANG_ENABLE	HANG_ENABLE - Hang the docker after the crash. Range: YES/NO If 'YES' then hanging will be enabled and autohealing will be disabled.	str	YES
RAN_ue_context_pool_size	#Number of predefined UE contexts in RAN (depends on available memory). Not a RAN UE limitation.	int	20
CU_IP	#O-CU IP. Format IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx). #NOTE: IP is filled in according to the example in the user manual	str	ran_cu550
DU_IP	#O-CU IP. Format IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx). #NOTE: IP is filled in according to the example in the user manual	str	ran_du550
RAN_cu_ip	#O-CU IP. Format IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx).	str	ran_cu550
RAN_du_ip	#O-CU IP. Format IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx).	str	ran_du550

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
CU_IP	#O-CU IP. Format IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx).	xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx
DU_IP	#O-DU IP. Format IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx).	xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx

Object Deployment Results:

It is necessary to create a jinja template from the markdown file that we will use as an output report when deploying the component. It must contain all the relevant information about the component itself so that the experimenter can use it.

IS-Wireless O-RAN

IS-Wireless O-RAN component has been successfully added to the Trial Network `{{ tn_id }}`

Important information:

This component will be available:

from: `{{ date_from }}`

to: `{{ date_to }}`

IS-Wireless O-RAN Frequency configuration:

- * NR frequency band number: `{{ RAN_band_indicator }}`
- * Absolute frequency position for downlink: `{{ RAN_pointa_arfcn_dl }}`
- * Absolute frequency position for uplink: `{{ RAN_pointa_arfcn_ul }}`
- * Global Synchronization Raster Channel: `{{ RAN_gscn }}`
- * ARFCN Value: `{{ RAN_ssb_arfcn }}`
- * k_SSB value: `{{ RAN_k_ssb }}`
- * Representation of the offset to Point A: `{{ RAN_offsetToPointA }}`
- * Index: `{{ RAN_config_idx }}`

3.1.3.2 OPENRAN_RIC

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
 - Yes
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image?
 - Yes
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace?
 - Yes (Private)
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Yes
 - Which networks?
 - INTERNET

- Is this object going to be available for all sites?
 - No (Only UMA)
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
- Yes
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?
 - two

Object information

Component Name: openran_RIC

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	openran_CUDU
Short Desc	Deployment of Near-RT RIC as Docker Image.
Long Desc	Simple description of IS-Wireless Near-RT RIC solution: https://www.is-wireless.com/networks/software/
Hypervisors	[one]
Sites	[uma]

Public Object Input Parameters:

Public variables are those whose value can be modified from the TNLCM portal.

Required input parameters add information that can't be set with defaults, like dependencies with other deployed components.

Variable types are currently int, str, intlist and strlist.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required_When
xApp_deploy_list	List of xApps to use.	strlist	NONE	KPM_MONITOR,HELLO_WORL,....	true

RIC_LOGLEVEL	# The log level of all containers	str	WARN		false
E2_PORT	# By using E2_PORT it is possible to configure Near-RT RIC E2 port	int	30421		false

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value
RC_FLIP_PERIOD	# RC_FLIP_PERIOD corresponds to the time period (in seconds) between each PRB quota flips	int	5
RC_SLICE_ID1	# RC_SLICE_IDx gives ID of the slice, so that it is assigned RC_QUOTAx respectively to the ID	int	1
RC_SLICE_ID2	# RC_SLICE_IDx gives ID of the slice, so that it is assigned RC_QUOTAx respectively to the ID	int	2
RC_QUOTA1	# RC_QUOTAx determines the ratio (in percentage) of available resources per slice	int	20
RC_QUOTA2=	# RC_QUOTAx determines the ratio (in percentage) of available resources per slice	int	80
RAN_ric_enable	Enable RIC usage	str	true
RAN_ric_ip	RIC IP	str	main

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
RIC_IP=	#RIC IP. Format IPv4 (xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx). #NOTE: IP is filled in according to the example in the user manual	10.100.0.2

Object Deployment Results:

It is necessary to create a jinja template from the markdown file that we will use as an output report when deploying the component. It must contain all the relevant information about the component itself so that the experimenter can use it

https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6GLibrary/blob/alt_architecture/open5gs/result_templates/ok_result.md.i2

IS-Wireless Near-RT RIC

IS-Wireless Near-RT RIC component has been successfully added to the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}

Important information:

This component will be available:

from: {{ date_from }}
to: {{ date_to }}

Selected configurations during deployment.

- * List of chosen xApps: {{ xApp_deploy_list }}
- * The log level of all containers: {{ RIC_LOGLEVEL }}
- * By using E2_PORT it is possible to configure Near-RT RIC E2 port: {{ E2_PORT }}

3.2 RIS IMPLEMENTATION

3.2.1 HW AND SW COMPONENTS

As mobile technology has been moving towards higher frequencies to obtain higher data rates, the challenge of working in the millimeter wave (mmWave) range (>24.45 GHz) is being faced by the entire industry. Signals in the mmWave bands are particularly affected by the environment, such as foliage, rain, people, glass and walls,

and the free-space path loss (FSPL). For this project in particular, the FSPL needs to be accurately modeled in order to provide us with the information about how large a RIS needs to be to aid a mmWave channel. In its simplest form, the FSPL is given by the equation below:

$$FSPL = \left(\frac{4\pi d}{\lambda} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

d is the distance between transmitter (TX) and receiver (RX), and λ is the wavelength which is inversely proportional to the frequency of the signal. As we can observe, FSPL increases with the square of the distance and the frequency, and therefore is much higher than sub-6GHz bands.

Moreover, as previously mentioned, high frequency signals are strongly affected by the surrounding environment and the presence of an obstacle such as a building or a tree are enough to block communications. To circumvent this issue, an RIS can be used to efficiently redirect the signal with direct line of sight (LoS) from TX to RX, as illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12: An RIS-aided mmWave network.

The RIS is composed of an array of metallic elements, called unit-cells, which are controlled by PIN diodes or varactors. Those components change the electromagnetic properties of the unit-cell and when controlled by a processing unit, reconfigures the reflection characteristics of the surface (hence the name, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface). When this is achieved, the RIS acts like a phased antenna array and can beamforming, sending the signal more concentrated towards the user equipment (UE), compensating for the FSPL, and avoiding obstacles.

For the purposes of this project, each unit-cell is controlled by two PIN diodes, each responsible for switching the state for the vertical and horizontal polarisations (the axis in which the electric field is oscillating), therefore it presents 1-bit per polarization. The PIN diodes are responsible for changing the phase of the reflected wave by switching between the states, and controlling the direction of the wave, as illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13: PIN diode controlled RIS. Depending on the biasing of the diode, the reflected beam can be directed to different UEs.

Figure 14 shows an example of the phase distribution of a 1-bit, 22x22 elements phased array configured to steer the beam by 45 degrees. Each colour represents a reflection phase at the top of the unit-cell. As the system is configured for 1-bit, each unit-cell only changes its reflection phase by 180 degrees.

Figure 14: Phase distribution over a phased array to perform beam-steering at 45 degrees.

By employing a similar technique to the RIS, and dynamically controlling the phase distribution over its elements, we can obtain a more reliable channel, where users are constantly receiving high gain signal transmitted towards their UEs.

The aim of this project is to supply a RIS which can be used to extend the coverage of a 6G testbed in the 27.05-27.50 GHz band, which belongs to the n257 (26.5-29.5 GHz) and n258 (24.25-27.5 GHz) bands. The RIS must be controllable from a remote site and able to switch the phase of individual unit cells to scan the reflected beam. We therefore need to follow the sequence of steps shown below to achieve the desired performance of the Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface.

1. Obtain electromagnetic (EM) characteristics of the PIN diode
2. Model the unit-cell to provide a phase shift between the two states of the PIN diode across the n261 band
3. Based on the performance of the designed unit-cell, estimate the channel path-loss to calculate the optimal size of the RIS
4. Develop the digital architecture of the RIS, which will be responsible for controlling the PIN diodes
5. Determine how the Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) will manage the phase of each unit-cell depending on the desired characteristics of the channel.

3.2.2 HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

3.2.2.1 UNIT-CELL DESIGN

The requirements of the RIS are based on what is provided by the Nokia Airscale radio unit in Malaga, which operates within the n257 5G mmWave band (26.5-29.5 GHz). Our objective is to achieve a 1-bit unit-cell design which is capable of operating on both polarizations and present an operational bandwidth comparable to the Nokia Airscale radio unit. Such unit-cell design by itself presents a unique wideband performance yet to be reported in the literature. A disruptive design is therefore needed to achieve the required bandwidth, which brings unique challenges to our RF team.

Within the scope of our project, the one-bit unit cell will be composed of two PIN diodes, each controlling the phase for the vertical and horizontal polarizations independently. To perform beamforming at 1-bit, the phase difference at the unit cell in the row and the column must be between the on and off states.

Our design is based on the idea proposed in [18], where passive elements were used to improve the angular stability of the unit cell whilst maintaining the required phase difference of 180 deg. For our purposes, we aim to maintain an angular stability from 15deg-45deg, and less than 20deg phase error. Figure 15 shows two proposed unit-cell designs. The pattern is to be made on a 1.52 mm thick Rogers 4003C substrate.

Figure 15: Proposed unit-cell designs.

3.2.2.2 UNIT-CELL PERFORMANCE

In CST Microwave Studio, a unit-cell simulation set-up, as previously shown in Figure 15. To obtain an accurate phase reading from the unit-cell, the reference plane is transferred to the top surface of the pattern. Figure 16 shows the magnitude of the reflection coefficient of the unit-cell for the diode on and off states.

Figure 16: Simulated reflection coefficient of the unit-cell.

Due to the resonance of the unit-cell and the losses of the diode when conducting current, the reflection coefficient is reduced, which impacts the performance of the unit-cell. In later sections we demonstrate that this reduction in the reflection coefficient does not heavily affect the performance of the RIS.

The phase performance over the n257 band for this unit-cell is depicted in Figure 17 where we observe an error lower than 20 deg over the entire band. In a practical scenario where the central operating frequency is 27.275 GHz and considering a 450MHz channel bandwidth, this error is lower than if the RIS from Figure 15(a) is used at 30 deg, surpassing any other RIS publicized in the open literature. That is not only important for the sake of precision when configuring the state of the unit-cell when it is operational, but we also need to consider the beam misalignment and losses which occur when beamforming with single bit phase shift which can reduce the directivity of the RIS by up to 4 dB. To illustrate the effect of discretisation, Figure 18 shows the example of a 20x20 phased array with 1-bit applied to steer the beam towards 15deg.

Figure 17: Phase difference between the unit-cell on and off. (a) 30 deg incidence and (b) 45 deg incidence.

Property	1-Bit Quantisation		No Quantisation	
	Uniform	Rectangular	Uniform	Rectangular
Array Type	Uniform	Rectangular	Uniform	Rectangular
Array Size	[20 20]		[20 20]	
Element Spacing (m)	[0.4458 0.4458]		[0.4458 0.4458]	
Array Normal	x		x	
Signal Frequencies	27.275 GHz		27.275 GHz	
Directivity at Steering Angle (dBi)	26.04		29.71	
Y-Axis Array Span (m)	0.09		0.09	
Z-Axis Array Span (m)	0.09		0.09	
Side Lobe Level (SLL) along Az plane (dB)	0		13.19	
Side Lobe Level (SLL) along El plane (dB)	6.82		13.25	

Figure 18: Array directivity comparison for 15 degree steering direction. Left: 1-bit discretisation; Right: no discretisation.

The phase distribution for the blue pattern on the right side of Figure 18 is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Phase distribution of a 20x20 elements phased array for steering at 15deg.

We can observe on the left pattern, not discretised, that the directivity is 28.52 dBi at 15deg, whereas on the pattern on the right, the blue plot is 4.5 dBi lower than the red (ideal). These losses need to be considered when we calculate the link budget within an RIS enabled environment. The next section will discuss the link budget to justify the selected size of the RIS.

3.2.2.3 LINK BUDGET ANALYSIS

For our study, we are considering a scenario where the RIS is at a distance of 30 m from the base station (BS) which contains a Nokia Airscale unit operating at n257 band. The user equipment (UE) is located a further 30 m from the RIS, and the angle of both BS and UE are to the RIS, and it is illustrated in Figure 20, which also contains the properties of the TX unit in Málaga.

Figure 20: Scenario considered for the link budget analysis.

The reference sensitivity for a UE is given by 3GPP and shown in Table 2 below [19].

Table 2. Reference sensitivity [19]

Operating band	REFSENS (dBm) / Channel bandwidth			
	50 MHz	100 MHz	200 MHz	400 MHz
n257	-88.3	-85.3	-82.3	-79.3
n258	-88.3	-85.3	-82.3	-79.3
n260	-85.7	-82.7	-79.7	-76.7
n261	-88.3	-85.3	-82.3	-79.3

For this scenario, we are considering a worst case where the UE is an omnidirectional receiver (2 dBi), and that some losses are present in the channel. The path loss was calculated using references [20] and [21].

The results showing the received power for a TX power of 24 dBm and 28 dBm are shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Analytical received power in a RIS enabled channel. The results are compared to the required receiver sensitivity at different channel bandwidths. (a) Nokia Aircscale transmitting at 24 dBm, (b) Nokia Aircscale transmitting at 28 dBm (maximum power).

The plots show a good agreement between two different path-loss models discussed in [20] and [21], where all the diodes are on, i.e., $|G|=0.84$, and G is the reflection coefficient of the unit-cells. We can observe that for a RIS $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$, i.e., 20×20 unit-cells (approx. 5mm per unit-cell), there is a good margin between the received power and the minimum required sensitivity level by the 3GPP standard on a 100 MHz bandwidth channel, previously established in our open call document. Moreover, using the same models in [20] and [21], at full TX power (28 dBm) and 100 MHz bandwidth, the omnidirectional UE can be at a distance of up to 70 m from the RIS and still be at the limit of the UE. This might be improved in a real-world scenario where the UE typically presents a higher gain than an omnidirectional antenna.

We therefore arrive on the following conclusions:

- A RIS containing 20×20 unit-cell recovers enough power to enable the link.
- Each unit-cell contains 2 PIN diodes, one for each polarisation, i.e., we expect to use a total of 800 MADP-000907-14020P PIN Diodes.
- Obtaining the actual gain of the UE used in the tests will provide more accurate estimates for the path-loss models.

To operate a 400 MHz bandwidth channel requires either a higher TX power, or a higher gain antenna on the UE.

3.2.3 RIS ARCHITECTURE

The Project is made up of 4 parts.

- A software interface including libraries used to configure and control the RIS;
- A communications port on the RIS for Control;
- A digital interface which can update the control signals at each unit cells;
- An array of unit cells which can have their phase controlled in two axis via shift registers (SR).

Parts 2 to 4 can be seen in Figure 22. There may be multiple RIS panels put together to increase the area of the RIS. If these multiple panels have individual or shared communications to the controlling software is not yet determined.

Figure 22: RIS block diagram

In terms of the physical design of the RIS, the PCB is separated into 3 different layers, RF layer, DC bias, and the digital control unit. An exploded view is shown in Figure 23, where it depicts how we expect to successfully implement the RIS with the designed unit-cell. The DC bias is controlled by the SR, commanded by the FPGA.

Figure 23: Exploded view of the unit-cell

The Prepreg or bondply substrate and thickness are not yet defined and it may depend on the availability of the material with the manufacturer.

3.2.4 RIS KPI

The KPIs of the RIS are identified below:

- Signal Reflection and Manipulation in terms of (a) Reflectivity of the surface, (b) Ability to redirect signals in desired directions, and (c) Precision of signal focusing.
- Channel Gain Enhancement in terms of (a) Gain achieved by the RIS in terms of signal power or SNR (depending upon the receiver being in signaling or non-signaling mode) (b) Enhancement of signal strength in desired directions.
- Coverage Area in terms of (a) Maximum range of operation for signal enhancement, and (b) Area within which reliable signal enhancements are provided.
- Energy Efficiency in terms of (a) Power consumption levels, (b) Energy harvesting capabilities (if applicable), and (c) Adaptation of energy usage based on system requirements.

- Reconfiguration Speed in terms of (a) Time required for the RIS to adapt to changing signal conditions, and (b) Faster reconfiguration for dynamic optimization comparable with the channel coherence time.
- Interference Mitigation in terms of (a) Ability to nullify or minimize unwanted signals, and (b) Reduction of multi-path effects for improved signal quality.
- Scalability in terms of (a) Deployment in various environments and scenarios, and (b) Factors such as the number of elements, system complexity, and integration ease.

3.2.5 6G LIBRARY OBJECT

The RIS component is now in the development phase. It will be added later.

3.3 NTN IMPLEMENTATION

3.3.1 NETWORK COMPONENTS

NTN Solutions deployed at 6G-SANDBOX testbeds are based on commercial solutions from providers Starlink. The Hardware inventory for these providers is depicted in the following Table 3:

Table 3. HW Inventory from Providers

Hardware Component	Starlink Enterprise
Satellite Antenna	Starlink High Performance Kit (575x511 mm) Electronic Phased Array
Modem/Router	WIFI Starlink router 802.11ac Dual Band
Power Supply	Dedicated Earth Terminal IP56

Figure 24 illustrates the specifications of the data plans and speeds provided by Starlink.

Data plans	Throughput	Data limit	Additional prioritized data
Priority (Fixed - Land only)		1 TB Prioritized data + unlimited standard traffic (not prioritized)	Optional, Billable in Gbps units
		2 TB Prioritized data + unlimited standard traffic (not prioritized)	
Mobile Priority (Land & Maritime)	Max Speed 350 Downlink / 40 Uplink (Mbps) Average (Expected) 40 - 220 Downlink / 8 - 25 Uplink (Mbps)	6 TB Prioritized data + unlimited standard traffic (not prioritized)	Optional for Land, Rivers and Lakes, Billable in Gbps units Required for maritime use to maintain active service in open waters, billed in units of 1Gbps
		50 GB Prioritized data + unlimited standard traffic (not prioritized) in Land, Rivers and Lakes. Not extra traffic in open waters	
		1 TB Prioritized data + unlimited standard traffic (not prioritized) in Land, Rivers and Lakes. Not extra traffic in open waters	
		5 TB Prioritized data + unlimited standard traffic (not prioritized) in Land, Rivers and Lakes. Not extra traffic in open waters	

Figure 24: Starlink data plan

3.3.2 DEPLOYMENT SCENARIOS/ USE CASES

NTN Networks will be available for 6G-SANDBOX Experimenters. They can request TN to be connected to Satellite and include resources in both the main Testbed facility and the Remote facility. A TN might be composed of a 5G Core at the Remote facility with an UPF deployed at Main one.

Though Experimenters can shape the configuration in the TN description, several scenarios and use cases have been identified in 6G-SANDBOX. Here we enumerate the main use cases:

5G Backhaul

In this use case, NTN Network will be used for connection gNodeB to 5G Core using Satellite as backhaul. 5G Core can be fully remote or it can be distributed having Control Plane and User Plane in different locations. Figure 25 depicts the 5G backhaul use case.

Figure 25: 5G backhaul use case

Multipath Connectivity

Málaga Testbed and Madrid Peñuelas resources can be connected using multiple connectivity options. Along the Satellite connection, the backup VPN can also route traffic between the two sites. MPTCP and MTIP protocols can be used to establish multipath connectivity between the two sites. Figure 26 represents the multi connectivity use case.

The Starlink Router is connected to UMA Datacenter switch through a CISCO router CPE using dedicated ethernet cable, using VLAN 120. This VLAN is distributed to the 6G-SANDBOX Datacenter using Subnet 10.120.111.0 /24. Trial Networks using NTN connectivity should include the 6G Library NTN component that enables the connectivity through the satellite.

Figure 26: Multi connectivity use case

3.3.3 NTN EMULATION

NTN emulation solution deployed at Athens testbed is based on OpenSAND. A Multi-Link Access scenario was initially developed in order to be used for testing and validation of the NTN emulator integration with the platform. In this scenario, depicted in Figure 27, the two OvSs were receiving OpenFlow command to steer the traffic either the Terrestrial path or the Non-Terrestrial path.

Figure 27: Multi-Link Access scenario using OpenSAND emulator for the Non-Terrestrial path

Furthermore, an investigation of the MPTCP protocol has been initiated, in order to develop a multi-connectivity (terrestrial & non-terrestrial path) scenario, in which OpenSAND will be used to emulate the non-terrestrial path.

Moreover, the development of an API for OpenSAND, since it lacks one, was deemed necessary. The FastAPI web framework was used for building this API. The first version of the API includes endpoints to:

- Start/Stop OpenSAND entities (Gateway, Satellite, Satellite Terminal) (Figure 28)
- Check the status of OpenSAND (running or not)
- Generate infrastructure.xml files for all entities
- Retrieve/Update the value of a specific element from the profile.xml, for a specific entity (Figure 29)

Figure 28: Endpoint to start OpenSAND entities

Figure 29: Endpoint to update the “delay_value” on the satellite terminal

3.3.4 6G LIBRARY OBJECT

This section will present the description of the OpenSAND 6G Library Object. It includes three different Objects, one for each different entity (Gateway, Satellite, Satellite Terminal).

3.3.4.1 OPENSAND_GW

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
Yes. The initial version will need to deploy 1 VM within the Trial Network.
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image?
 - Yes
- Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace?
 - Yes
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)

It depends on the topology of the Trial Network and the scenario of the experiment.

 - Which networks?
- Is this object going to be available for all sites?
 - Yes
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
 - Yes, it can also be deployed multiple times on the same Trial Network.
- How many simultaneous instances does it support?
 - No limit. It depends on the available resources of the Platform

Object information

Component Name: `openSAND_GW`

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	2 VXiLans, OpenSAND_SAT, OpenSAND_ST
Short Desc	OpenSAND (NTN Emulator) Gateway entity

Long Desc	This component is able to emulate a complete DVB-RCS2 – DVB-S2 system and thus it provides an emulated satellite network system. It can be deployed in the Trial Network and create an emulated Gateway entity that can be interconnected with various other components, depending on the Trial Network's topology (mandatory interconnection with an emulated Satellite entity). Documentation can be found at https://github.com/CNES/opensand
Hypervisors	[one]
Sites	[UMA, Athens, Fokus, Oulu]

Public Object Input Parameters:

For this first version of the emulated Gateway entity an initial configuration (xml files) will be provided, and the experimenter will not be able to modify anything at the instantiation time. After the instantiation, access to the VM will be granted and the experimenter will be able to make any configuration changes.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required When

Private Object Defaults:

For this first version of the emulated Gateway entity an initial configuration (xml files) will be provided.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
ips	Dictionary of VM addresses: key='VNet ID in OpenNebula', value='IP address'	10.10.200.50
vm_id	VM ID in OpenNebula	500

Object Deployment Results:

When the component is deployed, the following report will be generated:

```

### OpenSAND Gateway entity

# Deployment

The OpenSAND Gateway entity has been successfully deployed on the VM {{ vm_id }}. This deployment is part
of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}.

# Access to Virtual Machine

You will be able to access the VM through IP {{ ip_address }} with SSH connection.
    
```

3.3.4.2 OPENSAND_SAT

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
Yes. The initial version will need to deploy 1 VM within the Trial Network.
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? Yes
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace? Yes
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...) Yes
It depends on the topology of the Trial Network and the scenario of the experiment.
- Is this object going to be available for all sites? Yes
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
Yes, it can also be deployed multiple times on the same Trial Network.
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?
No limit. It depends on the available resources of the Platform.

Object information

Component Name: OpenSAND_SAT

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	1 VNet, OpenSAND_ST, OpenSAND_GW
Short Desc	OpenSAND (NTN Emulator) Satellite entity
Long Desc	This component is able to emulate a complete DVB-RCS2 – DVB-S2 system and thus it provides an emulated satellite network system. It can be deployed in the Trial Network and create an emulated Satellite entity that can be interconnected with various other components, depending on the Trial Network's topology (mandatory interconnection with an emulated Gateway entity and an emulated Satellite Terminal entity). Documentation can be found at https://github.com/CNES/opensand
Hypervisors	[one]
Sites	[UMA, Athens, Fokus, Oulu]

Public Object Input Parameters:

For this first version of the emulated Satellite entity an initial configuration (xml files) will be provided, and the experimenter will not be able to modify anything at the instantiation time. After the instantiation, access to the VM will be granted and the experimenter will be able to make any configuration changes.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required When

Private Object Defaults:

For this first version of the emulated Satellite entity an initial configuration (xml files) will be provided.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
ips	Dictionary of VM addresses: key='VNet ID in OpenNebula', value='IP address'	10.10.200.51
vm_id	VM ID in OpenNebula	501

Object Deployment Results:

When the component is deployed, the following report will be generated:

```

## OpenSAND Satellite entity

# Deployment

The OpenSAND Satellite entity has been successfully deployed on the VM {{ vm_id }}. This deployment is part of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}.

# Access to Virtual Machine
    
```

You will be able to access the VM through IP {{ ip_address }} with SSH connection.

3.3.4.3 OPENSAND_ST

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
Yes. The initial version will need to deploy 1 VM within the Trial Network.
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? Yes
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace? Yes
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...) Yes
It depends on the topology of the Trial Network and the scenario of the experiment.
- Is this object going to be available for all sites? Yes
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
Yes, it can also be deployed multiple times on the same Trial Network.
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?
No limit. It depends on the available resources of the Platform.

Object information

Component Name: OpenSAND_SAT

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	2 VNet, OpenSAND_SAT, OpenSAND_GW
Short Desc	OpenSAND (NTN Emulator) Satellite Terminal entity
Long Desc	This component is able to emulate a complete DVB-RCS2 – DVB-S2 system and thus it provides an emulated satellite network system. It can be deployed in the Trial Network and create an emulated Satellite Terminal entity that can be interconnected with various other components, depending on the Trial Network's topology (mandatory interconnection with an emulated Satellite entity). Documentation can be found at https://github.com/CNES/opensand
Hypervisors	[one]
Sites	[UMA, Athens, Fokus, Oulu]

Public Object Input Parameters:

For this first version of the emulated Satellite Terminal entity an initial configuration (xml files) will be provided, and the experimenter will not be able to modify anything at the instantiation time. After the instantiation, access to the VM will be granted and the experimenter will be able to make any configuration changes.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required When

--	--	--	--	--	--

Private Object Defaults:

For this first version of the emulated Satellite Terminal entity an initial configuration (xml files) will be provided.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
ips	Dictionary of VM addresses: key='VNet ID in OpenNebula', value='IP address'	10.10.200.52
vm_id	VM ID in OpenNebula	502

Object Deployment Results:

When the component is deployed, the following report will be generated:

```
## OpenSAND Satellite Terminal entity
```

```
# Deployment
```

```
The OpenSAND Satellite Terminal entity has been successfully deployed on the VM {{ vm_id }}. This deployment is part of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}.
```

```
# Access to Virtual Machine
```

```
You will be able to access the VM through IP {{ ip_address }} with SSH connection.
```

3.3.4.4 NTN NETWORK

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network? Yes
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? No
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace?
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Which networks? NTN Network

- Is this object going to be available for all sites? Probably
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks? No
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?

Assumptions

There are some networks by platform that are part of the physical infrastructure and are needed to reach services or equipment deployed on the platform premises.

This object allows the access to this networks from a trial network, adding an additional network interface to the trial network bastion and configure some network rules and routes to warranty the security and isolation between trial networks.

Object information

Component Name: NTN Network

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	No
Short Desc	Network to access NTN capability
Long Desc	This object allows the access to NTN platform network from a trial network, adding an additional network interface to the trial network bastion and configure some network rules and
Hypervisors	[one]
Sites	[uma, fokus]

Public Object Input Parameters:

Public variables are those whose value can be modified from the TNLCM portal.

Required input parameters add information that can't be set with defaults, like dependencies with other deployed components.

Variable types are currently int, str, intlist and strlist.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required When
ntn_is_default_route	Use NTN network as default route	str	No	Yes,No	
ntn_routes	List of subnets that will be routed through this network	[str]	""		

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
ntn_ip_address	NTN assigned on the NTN network	10.10.10.1
routes	List of subnets that will be routed through this network	[192.168.100.0/24, 10.11.32.0/16]

3.4 DETERMINISTIC NETWORKING IMPLEMENTATION

3.4.1 NETWORK COMPONENTS

This section presents the hardware and software components available at the University of Malaga testbed for deterministic networking technology enablers defined in Sections 2.4 and 2.5. To address the requirements of deterministic communications, we have combined the capabilities of Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) (Section

2.4) and network programming with P4 (Section 2.5). TSN provides a foundation for deterministic networking by offering time synchronization, traffic scheduling, and network redundancy features. However, TSN may not always provide the flexibility needed to adapt to the diverse requirements of different applications. P4 complements TSN by enabling the dynamic customization of network device behavior to optimize for specific deterministic use cases. The integration of TSN and P4 creates a solution that delivers the deterministic guarantees required for critical applications while also providing the flexibility to tailor the network to specific application demands. This combination enables us to achieve an enhanced level of deterministic networking performance.

First, Time-Sensitive Networking including wired (TSN network) and wireless (TSN and 5G networks) configurations.

- Wired configuration:
 - [HW] 1 Relyum TSN bridge – 4 ports
 - [HW] 2 Relyum TSN bridge/endpoint – 2 ports
 - [HW] 4 INTEL I210 TSN endpoints – 1 port
- Wireless configuration (includes wired configuration devices):
 - [HW] 1 Telit fn980m
 - [HW] 1 Nokia Radio Access Network
 - [SW] 1 Open5GS core network
 - [SW] TSN translators provided by the experimenter. Note that UMA can provide a first version developed using P4. However, this version is currently not compliant with the standard.
 - [SW] TSN AF (Application Function) provided by the experimenter. Note that UMA can provide a first version. However, this version is currently not compliant with the standard.

Second, networking programming with P4 includes the following components:

- [SW] Multiple virtual P4 BMv2 switches.
- [HW] 1 High-performance Intel Tofino switch.
- [SW] INT-P4 telemetry modules.
- [SW] UPF-P4 module.

3.4.2 NETWORK CONFIGURATION

On the one hand, there are two main network configurations for TSN.

First, the wired TSN configuration previously presented in Figure 30, where the TSN endpoints are connected through the TSN bridges. The TSN endpoints communicate their specific requirements to the CUC, which exchanges information with the CNC to configure the network to meet the traffic requirements of the different users and services.

Second, the wireless TSN configuration (well-known as TSN over 5G), where the 5G network acts as a transparent TSN bridge for the TSN endpoints. First, the TSN translators, DS-TT next to the 5G User Equipment (UE) and NW-TT next to the User Plane Function (UPF). Second, the TSN AF connected with CNC/CUC. Third, other 5G components such as Radio Access Network (RAN) and the Network Functions (NFs) in the 5G core. Finally, the TSN endpoints that send and receive traffic.

Figure 30: TSN over 5G architecture, including 5G network components.

However, the configuration of P4 modules follows an NG-SDN approach, as illustrated in Figure 31. This approach divides the module into two programmable planes: the data plane and the control plane.

- **Data Plane:** This physically implements algorithms that process data packets and is programmed using the specific P4 language. The P4 data plane is structured around Match-Action Tables (MAT). This data plane operates on a programmable P4 chip.
- **Control Plane:** This is responsible for dynamically managing the behavior of the data plane, enabling the implementation of more complex algorithms. It is programmed using a general-purpose programming language that features an API for the P4 data plane. In our case, we employ Python.

Figure 31: Configuration of P4 modules follow an NG-SDN approach.

Delving further into the control plane, responsible for dynamically managing the data plane, it relies on the insertion, modification, or deletion of rules in the MAT tables previously defined in the P4 data plane. The specific functionality of the control plane depends on each module:

- UPF Module
- INT Telemetry Module

3.4.3 DEPLOYMENT SCENARIOS/ USE CASES

The integration of the P4 modules in the TSN over 5G architecture results in the deployment scenario depicted in Figure 32. In this case, a few P4 targets (specific P4 device for which a P4 program is compiled) are used to implement different P4 modules. For example, the capabilities of TSN translators (DS-TT and NW-TT) such as adding/removing headers can be implemented using the P4 language, since the control plane can be used to manage the data plane dynamically as explained above. Also, the functionalities of the TSN AF could be completed using P4. Moreover, P4 targets in the end-to-end connection (e.g. backhaul) can be used for QoS and telemetry purposes (using the P4 telemetry module integrated in the 5GC).

Figure 32: P4 modules integration in the TSN over 5G architecture

3.4.4 6G LIBRARY OBJECT

This section will present the description of the deterministic networking 6G Library Object. It includes two different Objects, such as UPF-P4 BMv2 SW Module, and UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW Module.

3.4.4.1 UPF-P4 BMv2 SW MODULE

This document is a preliminary analysis of the integration of the **UPF-P4 BMv2 SW** module into the 6GLibrary. It is a **software component** built into a virtual machine.

The UPF-P4 BMv2 SW module in 6G-SANDBOX serves as a valuable tool in enhancing the transport network across all platforms, enabling the attainment of the requisite features for deterministic communications. These features consist of ensuring low latency, delivering quality of service, efficient traffic management, traffic prioritization, and reliability.

The UPF-P4 BMv2 software module is built on a virtual machine where two Docker containers are launched. On one side, a container contains the data plane, which is the BMv2 switch along with the Stratum OS. On the other side, another container contains the Python controller that controls the data plane.

Important: The UPF-P4 BMv2 SW Module is developed to be compatible with Open5GS core control. Therefore, this component depends on and requires Open5GS to be deployed to use its control part. The component works with Open5GS Release 16 (specifically it has been tested with v2.5.8). I have created a new section at the end of this document called "Necessary Configuration of Dependencies" to indicate the necessary configurations in the dependencies.

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
 - Answer: Yes. In a first version, the object is deployed in a virtual machine within the trial network.
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? Yes
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace? No yet.
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Answer: Yes, the component needs internet access (If the external PDN of N6 is configured towards the internet) and access to the RAN network available on the platform but in this case, it would be done through the trial network (bastion).
 - Which networks?
 - Internet and RAN.
- Is this object going to be available for all sites?
 - Answer: Yes.
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
 - Answer: No. It can be deployed in as many trial networks as desired. In the same trial network, it can only be deployed once.
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?
 - Answer: No limit.

Object information

Component Name: UPF-P4 BMv2 SW

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	Open5GS
Short Desc	Deployment of the NG-SDN UPF-P4 BMv2 2 SW module using Open5GS as core control.
Long Desc	The UPF-P4 BMv2 SW module deploys a fully functional UPF Release 16 function in a virtual machine using docker containers. Compatible with Open5GS control.
Hypervisors	[ONE]
Sites	[UMA, Athens, Focus, Oulu]

Public Object Input Parameters:

For this first version, the experimenter will not be able to modify anything and everything necessary will be as private parameters.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required When

--	--	--	--	--	--

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

Basically, the parameters that the UPF-P4 BMv2 SW needs are the different IPs & MACs of the different components it has connected:

- RAN → IPv4 & MAC of RAN N3.
- Core control Plane (SMF) → IPv4 & MAC of SMF N4.
- DN → IP & MAC of DN N6.

In this case, since it is a virtual machine deployed within the Trial Network and will have its own network and IPs, the component also needs to know the local IPs and MAC of its interfaces where it is listening:

- UPF-RAN → IPv4 & MAC of UPF N3.
- UPF-Core control Plane (SMF) → IPv4 & MAC of UPF N4.
- UPF-DN → IP & MAC of UPF N6.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value
SMF_IPV4_N4	IPv4 of the N4 interface of the SMF endpoint. It is the IPv4 of the SMF that controls the UPF with the PFCP protocol.	str	<The value that is configured in the Open5GS SMF>
SMF_MAC_N4	MAC of the N4 interface of the SMF endpoint (or router in case you need an IP jump).	str	<The value that is configured in the Open5GS SMF>
GNB_IPV4_N3	IPv4 of the N3 interface of the RAN endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the RAN>
GNB_MAC_N3	MAC of the N3 interface of the GNB endpoint (or router in case you need an IP jump).	str	<The value that is configured in the RAN>
DN_IPV4_N6	IPv4 of the N6 interface of the DN endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the DN>
DN_MAC_N6	MAC of the N6 interface of the DN endpoint (or router in case you need an IP jump).	str	<The value that is configured in the DN>

UPF_IPV4_N4	IPv4 of the N4 interface of the local UPF endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the interface of the virtual machine where the component is deployed>
UPF_MAC_N4	MAC of the N4 interface of the local UPF endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the interface of the virtual machine where the component is deployed>
UPF_IPV4_N3	IPv4 of the N3 interface of the local UPF endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the interface of the virtual machine where the component is deployed>
UPF_MAC_N3	MAC of the N3 interface of the local UPF endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the interface of the virtual machine where the component is deployed>
UPF_IPV4_N6	IPv4 of the N6 interface of the local UPF endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the interface of the virtual machine where the component is deployed>
UPF_MAC_N6	MAC of the N6 interface of the local UPF endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the interface of the virtual machine where the component is deployed>

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution.

The output values of the UPF-P4 BMv2 SW component will be the IPs and MAC of the different interfaces that the UPF has.

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
vm_id		452

UPF_IPV4_N4	IPv4 of the N4 interface of the UPF endpoint.	"10.0.4.1"
UPF_MAC_N4	MAC of the N4 interface of the UPF endpoint	"00:90:fb:79:89:5d"
UPF_IPV4_N3	IPv4 of the N3 interface of the UPF endpoint.	"10.0.3.1"
UPF_MAC_N3	MAC of the N3 interface of the UPF endpoint	"b4:6a:d4:62:15:8a"
UPF_IPV4_N6	IPv4 of the N6 interface of the UPF endpoint.	"10.0.6.1"
UPF_MAC_N6	MAC of the N6 interface of the UPF endpoint	"b4:6a:d4:62:15:8b"

Object Deployment Results:

When the component is deployed, the following report will be generated:

```
## UPF-P4 BMv2 SW
```

```
# Deployment
```

The UPF-P4 BMv2 SW module has been successfully deployed on the VM {{ vm_id }}. This deployment is part of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}.

Below is a summary of the docker components that have been deployed within the virtual machine:

- * Docker container DP-UPF: Executes the P4 UPF data plane.

- * Docker container CP-UPF: Run the data plane python controller.

```
# Access to Virtual Machine
```

You will be able to access the VM through IP {{ }} with SSH connection.

```
# Connections
```

The UPF-P4 BMv2 SW has been successfully connected to:

- * RAN IP: {{ GNB_IPV4_N3 }}

- * Control core 5G: {{ SMF_IPV4_N4 }}

- * DN external: {{ DN_IPV4_N6 }}

```
# Logs
```

You can consult the logs of the component deployment at IP {{ }}. (1)

(1) Access to logs is something that is not yet fully implemented but will be implemented in the future.

We can render this markdown file to PDF to send it to the experimenter or to HTML to integrate it directly into the TNLCM portal.

UPF-P4 BMv2 SW

Deployment

The UPF-P4 BMv2 SW module has been successfully deployed on the VM {{ vm_id }}. This deployment is part of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}. Below is a summary of the docker components that have been deployed within the virtual machine:

- Docker container DP-UPF: Executes the P4 UPF data plane.
- Docker container CP-UPF: Run the data plane python controller.

Access to Virtual Machine

You will be able to access the VM through IP {{ }} with SSH connection.

Connections

The UPF-P4 BMv2 SW has been successfully connected to:

- RAN IP: {{ GNB_IPV4_N3 }}
- Control core 5G: {{ SMF_IPV4_N4 }}
- DN external: {{ DN_IPV4_N6 }}

Logs

You can consult the logs of the component deployment at IP {{ }}.

Necessary Configuration of Dependencies

In this section, the required configurations in the components upon which the UPF-P4 BMv2 module relies for its proper functionality will be described.

Dependency: Open5GS (Mandatory)

- Open5GS v2.5.8: We have tested the UPF with open5GS version 2.5.8. With Open5GS versions of Release 17 (open5gs > 2.6.0) our UPF does not work.
- The UPF component/service of Open5GS must be disabled.
- In the SMF configuration file:
 - Configure the IPv4 and MAC of the UPF-P4 BMv2 component (PFCP – N4).
 - Configure the same UE pool subnet (and APN) that has been configured in the UPF-P4 BMv2 component.
 - Delete/Disable ipv6 on the subnet.
- Insert fixed ARP rule for UPF IP (UPF is not able to resolve ARP)

Dependency: UERANSIM (Optional)

- Insert fixed ARP rule for UPF IP (UPF is not able to resolve ARP)

Dependency: Nokia RAN (Optional)

- Insert fixed ARP rule for UPF IP (UPF is not able to resolve ARP)

3.4.4.2 UPF-P4 INTEL TOFINO 2 HW MODULE

This document is a preliminary analysis of the integration of the **UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW** module into the 6GLibrary. It is a **hardware component** integrated into the Intel Tofino 2 switch.

The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW module in 6G-SANDBOX serves as a valuable tool in enhancing the transport network of the Malaga infrastructure, enabling the attainment of the requisites features for deterministic communications. These features consist of ensuring low latency, delivering quality of service, efficient traffic management, traffic prioritization, and reliability.

The Intel Tofino 2 hardware switch has two parts. On one side, it has the Intel Tofino 2 chip where the P4 UPF data plane is executed. However, it has an Intel Pentium D1517 where the Ubuntu OS is installed and contains the python controller of the data plane. Therefore, for this module no external virtual machine is required and everything is contained in the hardware device.

Important: The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW Module is developed to be compatible with Open5GS core control. Therefore, this component depends on and forces Open5GS to be deployed to use its control part. The component works with Open5GS Release 16 (specifically it has been tested with v2.5.8). I have created a new section at the end of this document called “**Necessary Configuration of Dependencies**” to indicate the necessary configurations in the dependencies.

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
 - Answer: No. It is a hardware component that is already deployed on the Malaga platform.
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? No
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace? No
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Answer: Yes, the component needs internet access and access to the RAN network available on the Malaga platform.
 - Which networks?
 - Internet and RAN.
- Is this object going to be available for all sites?
 - Answer: No. The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 object will only be available on the Malaga platform.
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
 - Answer: Yes.
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?
 - Answer: This object only allows one simultaneous instance.

Object information

Component Name: *UPF-P4 intel Tofino 2 HW*

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	Open5GS
Short Desc	Deployment of the high-performance UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW module using Open5GS as core control.
Long Desc	The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW module deploys a fully functional UPF Release 16 function on the high-performance Intel Tofino 2 hardware switch. Compatible with Open5GS control.
Hypervisors Controller	[TNLCM] (1)
Sites	[UMA]

- (1) The idea is that the UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW will have a process listening for API requests to start and stop the UPF application (it executes several specific commands within the switch). With this, the TNLCM will send a request to start (or stop) the UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW.

Public Object Input Parameters:

For this first version, the experimenter will not be able to modify anything and everything necessary will be as private parameters.

Extra: SSH IP access will not be provided to the hardware switch because we could have licensing issues with Intel since the component has confidential documents and files.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required When

Private Object Defaults

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

Basically, the parameters that the UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW needs are the different IPs & MACs of the different components it has connected:

- RAN → IPv4 & MAC of RAN N3.
- Core control Plane (SMF) → IPv4 & MAC of SMF N4.

- DN → IP & MAC of DN N6.

The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 has its fixed IP and MAC for each of its interfaces (N3 UPF, N4 UPF and N6 UPF). Perhaps in the future they will need to be modified.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value
SMF_IPV4_N4	IPv4 of the N4 interface of the SMF endpoint. It is the IPv4 of the SMF that controls the UPF with the PFCP protocol.	str	<The value that is configured in the Open5GS SMF>
SMF_MAC_N4	MAC of the N4 interface of the SMF endpoint (or router in case you need an IP jump).	str	<The value that is configured in the Open5GS SMF>
GNB_IPV4_N3	IPv4 of the N3 interface of the RAN endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the RAN>
GNB_MAC_N3	MAC of the N3 interface of the GNB endpoint (or router in case you need an IP jump).	str	<The value that is configured in the RAN>
DN_IPV4_N6	IPv4 of the N6 interface of the DN endpoint.	str	<The value that is configured in the DN>
DN_MAC_N6	MAC of the N6 interface of the DN endpoint (or router in case you need an IP jump).	str	<The value that is configured in the DN>

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution.

The output values of the UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW component will be the IPs and MAC of the different interfaces that the UPF has.

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
UPF_IPV4_N4	IPv4 of the N4 interface of the UPF endpoint.	"10.173.0.203"
UPF_MAC_N4	MAC of the N4 interface of the UPF endpoint	"00:90:fb:79:89:5d"
UPF_IPV4_N3	IPv4 of the N3 interface of the UPF endpoint.	"10.0.3.1"

UPF_MAC_N3	MAC of the N3 interface of the UPF endpoint	"b4:6a:d4:62:15:8a"
UPF_IPV4_N6	IPv4 of the N6 interface of the UPF endpoint.	"10.0.6.1"
UPF_MAC_N6	MAC of the N6 interface of the UPF endpoint	"b4:6a:d4:62:15:8b"

Object Deployment Results:

When the component is deployed, the following report will be generated:

```
# UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW UMA

## Deployment

The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW module has been successfully deployed on the Intel Tofino 2 switch of the Málaga platform. This deployment is part of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}.

Below is a summary of the components that have been deployed within the Intel Tofino 2 switch:

* Intel Tofino 2 Chip - Executes the P4 UPF data plane.
* Intel Pentium D1517 - Hosts the Ubuntu OS and the Python controller for the data plane.

## Connections

The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW has been successfully connected to:

* RAN IP: {{ GNB_IPV4_N3 }}
* Control core 5G: {{ SMF_IPV4_N4 }}
* DN external: {{ DN_IPV4_N6 }}

## Logs

You can consult the logs of the component deployment at IP {{ }}. (1)
```

(1) Access to logs is something that is not yet fully implemented but will be implemented in the future.

We can render this markdown file to PDF to send it to the experimenter or to HTML to integrate it directly into the TNLCM portal.

UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW UMA

Deployment

The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW module has been successfully deployed on the Intel Tofino 2 switch of the Málaga platform. This deployment is part of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}. Below is a summary of the components that have been deployed within the Intel Tofino 2 switch:

- Intel Tofino 2 Chip - Executes the P4 UPF data plane.
- Intel Pentium D1517 - Hosts the Ubuntu OS and the Python controller for the data plane.

Connections

The UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 HW has been successfully connected to:

- RAN IP: {{ GNB_IPV4_N3 }}
- Control core 5G: {{ SMF_IPV4_N4 }}
- DN external: {{ DN_IPV4_N6 }}

Logs

You can consult the logs of the component deployment at IP {{ }}.

Necessary Configuration of Dependencies

In this section, the required configurations in the components upon which the UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 module relies for its proper functionality will be described.

Dependency: Open5GS (Mandatory)

- Open5GS v2.5.8: We have tested the UPF with open5GS version 2.5.8. With Open5GS versions of Release 17 (open5gs > 2.6.0) our UPF does not work.
- The UPF component/service of Open5GS must be disabled.
- In the SMF configuration file:
 - Configure the IPv4 and MAC of the UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 component (PCFP – N4).
 - Configure the same UE pool subnet (and APN) that has been configured in the UPF-P4 Intel Tofino 2 component.
 - Delete/Disable ipv6 on the subnet.
- Insert fixed ARP rule for UPF IP (UPF is not able to resolve ARP)

Dependency: UERANSIM (Optional)

- Insert fixed ARP rule for UPF IP (UPF is not able to resolve ARP)

Dependency: Nokia RAN (Optional)

- Insert fixed ARP rule for UPF IP (UPF is not able to resolve ARP)

3.4.4.3 TIME SENSITIVE NETWORKING

This document is a preliminary analysis of the integration of the **Time-Sensitive Networking** (TSN) equipment into the 6GLibrary. They are **hardware components** composed of a TSN Bridge and two TSN Endpoints.

The TSN equipment in 6G-SANDBOX serves as a valuable tool in enhancing the transport network of the Malaga infrastructure, enabling the attainment of the requisites features for deterministic communications. These features consist of ensuring low latency, delivering quality of service, efficient traffic management, traffic prioritization, and reliability.

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
 - No. It is a hardware component that is already deployed on the Malaga platform.
- Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image?
 - Not needed.
- Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace?
 - Not applicable.
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Some networks could be used depending on the use case.
- Which networks?
 - 5GC network (TSN over 5G), internet (TSN translators development), monitoring, etc.
- Is this object going to be available for all sites?
 - No, TSN will only be available on the Malaga platform.
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
 - Yes.
- How many simultaneous instances does it support?
 - This object only allows one simultaneous instance.

Object information

Component Name: Time-Sensitive Networking

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

Dependencies	Depending on the use case
Short Desc	Time-Sensitive Networking equipment
Long Desc	Time-Sensitive Networking equipment available on the Malaga platform, including 2 TSN endpoints (Relyum) and 1 TSN bridge (Relyum)
Hypervisors	[one]
Sites	[UMA]

Public Object Input Parameters:

Public variables are those whose value can be modified from the TNLCM portal.

Required input parameters add information that can't be set with defaults, like dependencies with other deployed components.

Variable types are currently int, str, intlist and strlist.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Default Value	Choices	Required When
TSN_BRIDGE_NUMBER	Number of TSN Bridges to be instantiated	int	1	[1]	false
TSN_ENDPOINT_NUMBER	Number of TSN Endpoints to be instantiated	int	2	[1-2]	false

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

Parameter Name	Short Description	Type	Value
TSN_BRIDGE_1_IPV4	TSN bridge #1 IPv4 address	str	192.168.2.10
TSN_ENDPOINT_1_IPV4	TSN endpoint #1 IPv4 address	str	192.168.2.100
TSN_ENDPOINT_2_IPV4	TSN endpoint #2 IPv4 address	str	192.168.2.200

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution

Output Parameter Name	Short Description	Example Value
TSN_BRIDGE_1_IPV4	TSN bridge #1 IPv4 address	192.168.2.10
TSN_ENDPOINT_1_IPV4	TSN endpoint #1 IPv4 address	192.168.2.100
TSN_ENDPOINT_2_IPV4	TSN endpoint #2 IPv4 address	192.168.2.200

Object Deployment Results:

Time-Sensitive Networking Trial Network

The Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) Trial Network (TN) architecture is shown below, in which 2 TSN endpoints are interconnected through a TSN bridge.

![TSN_TN](TSN_TN.png)

TSN configuration

The TSN configuration can be performed via SSH (cli) using a terminal or dashboard (gui) using a browser. Details on how to configure the different TSN features can be found in the [TSN configuration guide](TSN_TN_configuration_guide.pdf). For example, the following command is used to configure the Time Aware Shaper (IEEE 802.1Qbv):

```
``sh
spt_config_reg -n 0 -w qbv_config_file.json
````
```

In this case, the specific parameters are defined in [qbv\_config\_file.json](qbv\_config\_file.json) and are applied only on port 0 of the device (indicated by -n 0). The following image shows the TSN configuration defined in [qbv\_config\_file.json](qbv\_config\_file.json).

![TAS\_gui\_example](TAS\_gui\_example.png)

The TSN configuration can also be checked using the command:

```
``sh
spt_qbv_config -n 0 -r
````
```

Note that only the administrative values are shown. However, the operative values will be the same and are also shown in the command output:

```
``sh
-----
Port ID: 0
Gate Enabled: 0

-----
Administrative values
-----
Gate States: 255
Control List Length: 6

-----
Control List
-----

Index: 0
Operation Name: set-gate-states
Gate States Value: 32
Time Interval Value: 10000000

Index: 1
Operation Name: set-gate-states
Gate States Value: 1
Time Interval Value: 10000000

Index: 2
Operation Name: set-gate-states
Gate States Value: 8
```

Time Interval Value: 10000000

Index: 3

Operation Name: set-gate-states

Gate States Value: 4

Time Interval Value: 10000000

Index: 4

Operation Name: set-gate-states

Gate States Value: 128

Time Interval Value: 10000000

Index: 5

Operation Name: set-gate-states

Gate States Value: 82

Time Interval Value: 10000000

Cycle Time Numerator: 60000000

Cycle Time Denominator: 1000000000

Cycle Time Extension: 1000

Base Time Seconds: 0

Base Time Nanoseconds: 0

'''

Login Credentials

Information required to access the TSN components of the trial network.

| Device | IP address | User | Password | Connection |
|-------------------|---------------|--------|----------|------------|
| ----- | ----- | ----- | ----- | ----- |
| TSN endpoint 1 PC | X.X.X.X | tsnep1 | tsnep1 | SSH or VNC |
| TSN endpoint 2 PC | X.X.X.X | tsnep2 | tsnep2 | SSH or VNC |
| TSN endpoint 1 | 192.168.2.100 | relyum | relyum | SSH |
| TSN endpoint 1 | 192.168.2.100 | admin | relyum | Dashboard |
| TSN endpoint 2 | 192.168.2.200 | relyum | relyum | SSH |
| TSN endpoint 2 | 192.168.2.200 | admin | relyum | Dashboard |
| TSN bridge | 192.168.2.10 | relyum | relyum | SSH |
| TSN bridge | 192.168.2.10 | relyum | admin | Dashboard |

Time-Sensitive Networking Trial Network

The Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) Trial Network (TN) architecture is shown below, in which 2 TSN endpoints are interconnected through a TSN bridge.

TSN configuration

The TSN configuration can be performed via SSH (cli) using a terminal or dashboard (gui) using a browser. Details on how to configure the different TSN features can be found in the [TSN configuration guide](#). For example, the following command is used to configure the Time Aware Shaper (IEEE 802.1Qbv):

```
spt_config_reg -n 0 -w qbv_config_file.json
```

In this case, the specific parameters are defined in [qbv_config_file.json](#) and are applied only on port 0 of the device (indicated by -n 0). The following image shows the TSN configuration defined in [qbv_config_file.json](#).

3.4.4.4 INT-P4 BMv2 SW MODULE

This document is a preliminary analysis of the integration of the **INT-P4 BMv2 SW** module into the 6GLibrary. It is a **software component** built into a virtual machine.

The INT-P4 telemetry module in 6G-SANDBOX serves as a component for enhancing network visibility and performance across the platform. By leveraging the P4 language and Network In-band Telemetry (INT) framework, it enables real-time monitoring and data collection directly from the data plane. This capability allows for efficient gathering of vital network metrics such as latency, hop count, and other performance indicators, without requiring control plane intervention. The INT-P4 module plays a role in maintaining the expected end-to-end quality in deterministic networks, facilitating quick detection and response to performance degradations, and ultimately contributing to the optimization of packet forwarding paths for improved network reliability and reduced latency.

The INT-P4 BMv2 software component consists of:

- One mandatory VM that contains the INT monitoring system (also called collector system).
- Two or more VMs that each contains an INT P4 application. Each P4 application is composed of two Docker containers:
 - Container 1: Contains the P4 data plane, which consists of the BMv2 switch along the Stratum OS.
 - Container 2: Contains the Python controller, that manages the P4 data plane.

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
 - Answer: Yes. In a first version, the object is deployed in several virtual machines within the trial network. There will be a minimum of 3 VMs (1 for the collector and 2 for the INT-P4 application). The TN owner will be asked how many INT-P4 switches he wants.
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? Yes
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace? No yet.
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Answer: Yes, the component needs access internet access and maybe access to the RAN network available on the platform. Access to the RAN network will depend on whether the experimenter configures an external RAN for the trial network and wants to monitor telemetry.
 - Which networks?
 - Internet and RAN.
- Is this object going to be available for all sites?
 - Answer: Yes.
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
 - Answer: No. It can be deployed in as many trial networks as desired.
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?
 - Answer: No limit.

Object information

Component Name: INT-P4 BMv2 SW

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

| | |
|--------------|--|
| Dependencies | |
| Short Desc | Deployment of the INT-P4 BMv2 SW module used to provide in-band telemetry within a 5G core network. |
| Long Desc | The INT-P4 BMv2 SW module deploys a set of virtual machines with the aim of performing in-band telemetry of GTP-U packets in a 5G core network. It allows monitoring of various metrics such as the input and output interfaces of packets, the internal latency of each hop, and the end-to-end latency. It enables visualization of these metrics using Grafana. |
| Hypervisors | [ONE] |
| Sites | [UMA, Athens, Focus, Oulu] |

Public Object Input Parameters:

The component has two types of VM: One is the collector that has its own configuration; and another is an INT-P4 switch type VM that can have three types of operation depending on the configuration that is established:

- Source type configuration.
- Transit type configuration.
- Sink type configuration.

The configuration for each VM is determined through the TNLCM portal and is specified by the TN owner.

The process begins with the TNLCM portal asking the TN owner (experimenter) to specify the number of INT-P4 switch VMs required (minimum 2). Afterward, the portal inquiries about the configuration for each switch individually, asking the TN owner to designate each switch as either a 'Source', 'Transit', or 'Sink' and to provide the corresponding public parameters for each type of configuration.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|---------------------------|---|---------|--------------------|-----------------------------|---------------|
| int_p4_switch_count | Number of INT-P4 switches wanted. | int | 2 | | False |
| int_p4_switch_config_type | Configuration type of each INT-P4 switch. | strlist | ['Source', 'Sink'] | 'Source', 'Transit', 'Sink' | False |

Public object input parameters for collector VM:

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|----------------|-------------------|------|---------------|---------|---------------|
| | | | | | |

Public object input parameters for INT-P4 VM of type Source:

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|-------------------|---|------|---------------|---------|---------------|
| next_hop_dest_mac | Destination MAC address of the next hop for the GTP-U packet | str | "" | | |
| int_instruction | INT instructions are encoded as a bitmap in the 16-bit INT Instruction field. (1) Used to indicate what telemetry to extract at each hop. | str | "0xEC00" | | False |

(1) Meaning of each bit:

- bit0 (MSB): Switch ID
- bit1: Level 1 Ingress Port ID (16 bits) + Egress Port ID (16 bits)
- bit2: Hop latency
- bit3: Queue ID (8 bits) + Queue occupancy (24 bits)
- bit4: Ingress timestamp
- bit5: Egress timestamp
- bit6: Level 2 Ingress Port ID + Egress Port ID (4 bytes each)
- bit7: Egress port Tx utilization
- bit15: Checksum Complement
- The remaining bits are reserved. Each instruction requests 4 bytes of metadata to be inserted at each hop, except if bit 6 is set, which requires 8 bytes of metadata. Per-hop metadata length is set accordingly at the INT source.

Public object input parameters for INT-P4 VMs of type Transit:

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|-------------------|---|------|---------------|---------|---------------|
| next_hop_dest_mac | Destination MAC address of the next hop | str | "" | | |

| | | | | | |
|--|----------------------|--|--|--|--|
| | for the GTP-U packet | | | | |
| | | | | | |

Public object input parameters for INT-P4 VM of type Sink:

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|-------------------|--|------|---------------|---------|---------------|
| next_hop_dest_mac | Destination MAC address of the next hop for the GTP-U packet | str | "" | | |
| | | | | | |

Private Object Defaults:

Same structure as the case of Public Object Input Parameters.

Private object defaults for collector VM:

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Value |
|----------------|---|------|-------|
| mon_int | Local Monitoring interface through which reports are received from the VM that contains an INT-P4 switch with SINK configuration. | str | <> |

Private object defaults for INT-P4 VM of type Source:

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Value |
|----------------|-------------------|------|-------|
| | | | |

Private object defaults for INT-P4 VMs of type Transit:

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Value |
|----------------|-------------------|------|-------|
| | | | |

Public object input parameters for INT-P4 VM of type Sink:

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Value |
|----------------|---|------|-------|
| collector_ipv4 | IPv4 of the VM that contains the collector. | str | <> |
| collector_mac | MAC of the VM that contains the collector. | str | <> |

Object Output Values:

Object Output Values for collector VM:

| Output Parameter Name | Short Description | Example Value |
|-----------------------|-------------------|---------------|
| vm_id | | 452 |

Object Output Values for each INT-P4 VM of type Source, Transit or Sink:

| Output Parameter Name | Short Description | Example Value |
|-----------------------|-------------------|---------------|
| vm_id | | 452 |

| | | |
|------------------|---|---------------------|
| input_port_ipv4 | IPv4 of the GTP_U user data entry interface. | "10.0.1.1" |
| output_port_mac | MAC of the GTP_U user data entry interface. | "AA:BB:CC:DD:EE:F1" |
| output_port_ipv4 | IPv4 of the GTP_U user data output interface. | "10.0.2.1" |
| output_port_mac | MAC of the GTP_U user data entry interface. | "AA:BB:CC:DD:EE:F2" |

Object Deployment Results:

When the component is deployed, the following report will be generated:

```

# INT-P4 BMv2 SW
## Deployment
The INT-P4 BMv2 SW module has been successfully deployed on different VMs {{ vm_id_list }}. This deployment is part of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}.
## Access to the Virtual Machines
You can access the VMs through their respective IP addresses using SSH. The specific IP addresses for each VM are listed below.
## Virtual Machines (VMs) and Their IP Addresses
Connection to any of the VMs can be established via SSH using the following IP addresses:
### Collector VM
- **Collector VM**
  - IP Address: `x.x.x.x`

### INT-P4 Switch VMs
#### Source Type Configuration
- **Source VM**
  - IP Address: `x.x.x.x`
#### Transit Type Configuration
- **Transit VM 1**
  - IP Address: `x.x.x.x`
- **Transit VM 2**
  - IP Address: `x.x.x.x`
- _[Add more Transit VMs as needed..._]
#### Sink Type Configuration
- **Sink VM**
  - IP Address: `x.x.x.x`
---
*Note: Replace `x.x.x.x` with the actual IP addresses for each VM.*
# Logs
You can consult the logs of the component deployment at IP {{ }}. (1)
  
```

(1) Access to logs is something that is not yet fully implemented but will be implemented in the future.

We can render this markdown file to PDF to send it to the experimenter or to HTML to integrate it directly into the TNLCM portal.

UPF-P4 BMv2 SW

Deployment

The INT-P4 BMv2 SW module has been successfully deployed on different VMs {{ vm_id_list }}. This deployment is part of the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}.

Access to the Virtual Machines

You can access the VMs through their respective IP addresses using SSH. The specific IP addresses for each VM are listed below.

Virtual Machines (VMs) and Their IP Addresses

Connection to any of the VMs can be established via SSH using the following IP addresses:

Collector VM

- Collector VM
 - IP Address: x.x.x.x

INT-P4 Switch VMs

Source Type Configuration

- Source VM
 - IP Address: x.x.x.x

Transit Type Configuration

- Transit VM 1
 - IP Address: x.x.x.x
- Transit VM 2
 - IP Address: x.x.x.x
- [Add more Transit VMs as needed...]

Sink Type Configuration

- Sink VM
 - IP Address: x.x.x.x

Note: Replace x.x.x.x with the actual IP addresses for each VM.

Logs

You can consult the logs of the component deployment at IP {{ }}. (1)

3.5 XR IMPLEMENTATION

3.5.1 HW AND SW COMPONENTS (DEVICES AND SENSORS)

Two types of XR devices are involved in the development of the 6G-SANDBOX Library: 1) an immersive communication system; and 2) haptic devices.

3.5.2 IMMERSIVE COMMUNICATION SYSTEM

Figure 33: An Immersive Communication System

Figure 33 shows an immersive communication system. As commented before, the Owl is one of the devices used in the use case. It is a bi-directional real-time immersive telepresence system that focuses on the real-time capture, delivery and rendering of real spaces, including the people that are present in them. It incorporates a 360-degree camera that captures and transmits, in real-time, audio and 360 video to those who are connected to the session using commercial VR devices. In turn, the VR devices transmit the user's hands and head movements which are displayed in remote locations. Its simplified architecture is shown in the figure above. The camera is plugged into a Single Board Computer with a touch screen in charge of the capturing and streaming logic, a 6G/5G modem, a commercial hands-free speaker/microphone and a power bank as the power supply for all the devices. All the components are placed together in a 3D-printed custom housing, which can be either mounted on a tripod or placed on a flat surface.

Captured video from the 360 camera is compressed and streamed in H.264 format with a customizable bitrate and a video resolution of up to 4K. A backend is required to be deployed close to the 6G/5G network and using the XR extension module. It is in charge of orchestrating the video streams requested by multiple users using RTP transmission. It includes a session control handling the required signaling, coded in Python, and a scalable video processing module coded in C. The backend allows scaling the service to many users as well as enhancing the real-time video streams with additional Augmented Reality (AR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) capabilities by adding processing power in dedicated GPU hardware.

3.5.3 HAPTIC VEST DEVICES

OWO's API is needed in order seamlessly interconnect any VR/XR experience with the haptic sensations. This API has two main blocks:

- **Communication:** Allows the integration of the library in other non-native software.
- **Sensations:** contains all the functionalities that can be implemented in the Haptic system.

This allows any other company or group to develop their own sensations and integrate them in their apps, devices or implementations.

The steps to follow in order to create a haptic project are:

1. Setting up the plug-ins
2. Configuring the software project
3. Connecting
4. Creating the sensations
5. Sending the sensations.

Further detailed documentation can be found in our gitbook [22].

Besides, OWO's haptic vest is controlled with the interconnection of a wireless device and an app that controls the sensations. The communication protocol requires both 5G and Bluetooth communication. Therefore, OWO provides a real use-case network where quality and latency are critical for performance.

Network Configuration

Figure 34: XR extension network configuration

Figure 34 depicts an XR extension network configuration. The XR extension is an abstraction layer that acts as a bridge, enabling the translation of high-level network configuration and management commands to run XR applications into actions that the 5G network can execute.

The XR extension will play a crucial role in enhancing the management and delivery of XR content by optimizing delivery. It also abstracts to the application developers the details of the network configuration. Its functional view is depicted in the figure above. This extension will be provided as a **Python module that runs in a server, initially outside the 6G/5G network** but with access to the NaC library of it via REST API.

As part of the XR Extension, the following concepts are defined:

- **XRQoS**: quality of service required for a data flow within an XR service. It may be defined in terms of bitrate, latency, data loss rate, etc.
- **XRStream**: data stream between two peers (endpoint and server, usually) with specific QoS requirements.
- **XRSession**: set of Streams used by an XR service for a particular user or group of users over a time period.

The software module that will be installed in the server (the XR extension) will map the XRStreams (and hence the XRSessions) into the proper network parameters (e. g. slices). The functionality of this module can be divided into:

- Resource Provisioning: allocate network resources, usually distributed in “pipes” with different QoS capabilities.
- Stream/Session Management: create/delete/modify XRStreams and XRSessions
- Runtime Notifications: about upcoming usage of resources, changes in the network or statistics.
- KPI/KVI storage/retrieval.

Developers willing to make use of this module only need to import the right python module that will be able to manage the resources without any knowledge of the 6G/5G network configuration.

3.5.4 WORKFLOW

The typical workflow of an XR application using the XR extension library would be like this:

1. Initialize the library. This will make all the initial handshaking with the network for authentication, initialization of resources, etc.
2. Create as many XRStreams objects as needed for the flows used by the application. This may include video and audio generated by cameras, metadata, pose and position information, control commands, etc. Each stream will be defined with a source and destination (though an ID, or an IP address) that will

be used by the network to select the appropriate data paths. Each stream is also assigned a relative priority, identifying its importance with respect to other streams that are launched within the same session.

3. Create a session (XRSession) with a set of streams. This will inform the network about the streams that will need to be online (and their requirements) when the session starts. It is here where the network will allocate streams to network paths. It is also possible to give priority to the session, which may be used later to prioritize some sessions over others. An XR session will typically include the streams of all devices (and users) connected to the same communication session.
4. Read from each XRStream object the interfaces and addresses to be used to send data. This way, the XR application will know how to send data to the specific paths that the network has reserved for each stream with the appropriate QoS.
5. Start the session. If everything goes well the network will do some accounting and return an ok, reporting that the application can start sending data. In some cases, it is possible that the resources required by the session cannot be allocated at this moment (due to the current status of the network, which may have many other sessions running), and it will report so. The application should not start, instead it should do one of these actions:
 - a. Reassign priorities to streams and get back to step 3
 - b. Modify the session priority and try again.
 - c. Wait and try again.
6. Send data. During the session the network may need to inform the application about potential problems in the delivery, either because of changes in the conditions (links' quality getting lower, users moving to worse physical places, etc.) or because of other users with higher priority getting into scene. The application should use this information to change its own behavior and adapt to the new circumstances.
7. Optionally, create new XRStreams and add them to the session. This may be required, e.g., if new users want to join a communication session. Similarly, if users abandon the application the network should be informed by removing the corresponding XRStreams from the session.
8. When the application has fully finished the session is stopped. If it is not planned to start again it should be deleted.

Note that this workflow assumes that the network configuration has been done beforehand. This means that the available “pipes” and their associated network resources are static and do not change during the execution of XR sessions. At a later stage we will add the possibility of dynamically changing the network configuration to allocate more resources or redistribute the existing ones. The XR Extension uses the Network as Code paradigm, using a real implementation on the testbed.

3.5.5 DEPLOYMENT SCENARIOS/ USE CASES

The XR application that will be used to do the integration and testing of the XR Extension module will be the Nokia Telepresence application, that provides a full end-to-end communication system with immersive technology. Some sample real-life applications:

- **Remote expert:** in scenarios where the help of these use cases in the problem to be solved having that person present there virtually enables a much more efficient assistance. This can be applied to many environments: manufacturing, healthcare, retail, education, etc.
- **Meetings:** when the local space where the meeting takes place is important, remote participants would like to feel as being there, not only as a small window in a screen or a hands-free device in a corner. Immersive telepresence provides a much better experience. This is applicable to personal meetings, commercial events, trade shows, tourism, real estate, etc.

- **Surveillance:** security applications requiring physical exploration of a space where there are other persons can benefit from this technology, avoiding the need of security personnel to be physically there.
- **Interaction:** if we have a digital twin of the space where action is happening the users of an immersive telepresence application can not only feel present and talk with others, but also actuate on real devices in the place.

It might be noticed that not all of these use cases can be tested over the project duration. These might be deployed and tested as part of future Open Calls. Furthermore, the applications are not limited to these scenarios but any other else might make use of the XR Extension.

3.5.6 RESULTS AND FINDINGS (IMPACT OF XR)

At this stage of the project, there is no implementation of any use case yet. So, no result can be provided. This will be included in the next iteration of the 6G-SANDBOX Library in Deliverable 3.3.

3.5.7 6G LIBRARY OBJECT

This section will describe the XR library object, e.g., XRExt.

3.5.7.1 XREXT

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
 - No, it is based on the NaC server already deployed into UMA testbed lab.
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image?
 - No
- Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace?
 - Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Yes
 - Which networks? Nokia Radio UMA Network
- Is this object going to be available for all sites?
 - No, only at UMA
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks?
 - No, but as radio resources are limited, it is convenient to schedule trials properly.
- How many simultaneous instances does it support?

Assumptions:

The object consists of a Python package that includes several modules, some of them public, and two others specific that implement:

- the client part to communicate with NaC server
- the management of XR sessions: allocation of XR streams and assignments of IMSIs to slices

The configuration required to connect to the NaC server must be included into a file “config.ini” located in the same directory as the Python script that executes the trial:

```
[NacService]
host = 10.182.32.52
port = 8005
username = TBD
```

```
password = ***

[CapifService]
http_host = capifcore
http_port = 8080
https_host = capifcore
https_port = 443
username = TBD
password = ***
invoker_id = ***
api_name = nac_api
```

An appliance will be created that includes the client library, since it is a private development. It will not be uploaded to the marketplace because it is a component that will only be on the UMA site.

Object information

Component Name: XRErt

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

| | |
|--------------|---|
| Dependencies | |
| Short Desc | XR sessions on UMA NaC-managed 5G network |
| Long Desc | The XRExt component offers creation of XR sessions on top of the resources of the 5G network deployed at UMA site, through the services provided by NaC |
| Hypervisors | [one] |
| Sites | [uma] |

Public Object Input Parameters:

Public variables are those whose value can be modified from the TNLCM portal.

Required input parameters add information that can't be set with defaults, like dependencies with other deployed components.

Variable types are currently int, str, intlist and strlist.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|----------------|-------------------|------|---------------|---------|---------------|
| N/A | | | | | |

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Value |
|------------------------|-------------------------|------|--------------|
| xr_nac_server_ip | NAC server IP address | srt | 10.182.32.52 |
| xr_nac_server_port | NAC server port | srt | 8005 |
| xr_nac_server_username | NAC server username | srt | User |
| xr_nac_server_password | NAC server password | srt | Pass |
| xr_capif_http_host | CAPIF http URL | srt | Capifuma |
| xr_capif_http_port | CAPIF http port | srt | 8080 |
| xr_capif_https_host | CAPIF https URL | srt | Capifuma |
| xr_capif_https_port | CAPIF https port | srt | 443 |
| xr_capif_username | CAPIF register username | srt | Capifuser |
| xr_capif_password | CAPIF register password | srt | Capifpass |
| xr_capif_api_name | CAPIF API name | srt | nac_api |

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution

| Output Parameter Name | Short Description | Example Value |
|------------------------|-----------------------|---------------|
| xr_vm_id | OpenNebula VM ID | 1235 |
| xr_vm_ip | OpenNebula VM IP | 10.11.32.7 |
| xr_nac_server_ip | NAC server IP address | 10.182.32.52 |
| xr_nac_server_port | NAC server port | 8005 |
| xr_nac_server_username | NAC server username | User |
| xr_nac_server_password | NAC server password | Pass |
| xr_capif_http_host | CAPIF http URL | Capifuma |
| xr_capif_http_port | CAPIF http port | 8080 |

| | | |
|---------------------|-------------------------|-----------|
| xr_capif_https_host | CAPIF https URL | Capifuma |
| xr_capif_https_port | CAPIF https port | 443 |
| xr_capif_username | CAPIF register username | Capifuser |
| xr_capif_password | CAPIF register password | Capifpass |
| xr_capif_api_name | CAPIF API name | nac_api |

3.6 ADDITIONAL COMPONENTS

3.6.1 6G LIBRARY OBJECT

In this section, we provide some additional 6G library objects that will be included in the 6G-SANDBOX.

3.6.1.1 TEST CAMPAIGN MANAGER RUNNER

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network? Yes. We expect one instance per Trial network
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? Yes, this object is created as OpenNebula-appliance.
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace? Yes. It will be uploaded to OpenNebula's marketplace.
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...) yes
 - Which networks? This object needs to communicate with KS8500 server hosted by AWS via public internet.
- Is this object going to be available for all sites? yes
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks? No
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support? No limit in principle.

Object information

Component Name: Test Campaign Manager Runner

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

| | |
|--------------|---|
| Dependencies | no |
| Short Desc | Test Campaign Runner |
| Long Desc | This component allows experimenters to execute the test campaigns or test plans, which are created in Keysight's Test Campaign Manager Cloud (KS8500) |
| Hypervisors | [one] |
| Sites | Malaga, Athens, Berlin, Oulu |

Public Object Input Parameters:

Public variables are those whose value can be modified from the TNLCM portal.

Required input parameters add information that can't be set with defaults, like dependencies with other deployed components.

Variable types are currently int, str, intlist and strlist.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|----------------|--|------|---------------|---------|---------------|
| tn_id | Id of the Trial network | int | 1 | | true |
| user_token | User token used for deployment of runner | str | "" | | true |
| runner_name | Name of the runner to be deployed | str | "" | | true |

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Value |
|---------------------------|---|------|---|
| test_campaign_manager_url | Url to Keysight Test Campaign Manager Cloud | str | https://test-automation.pw.keysight.com |
| runner_image_file | File name of appliance | str | Testcampaign_runner |

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values or values generated during execution

| Output Parameter Name | Short Description | Value |
|---------------------------|---|---|
| test_campaign_manager_url | Url to Keysight Test Campaign Manager Cloud | https://test-automation.pw.keysight.com |
| tn_id | Trial network Id | 1 |
| runner_name | Name of the runner being deployed | "" |

Object Deployment Results:

It is necessary to create a jinja template from the markdown file that we will use as an output report when deploying the component. It must contain all the relevant information about the component itself so that the experimenter can use it.

Test Campaign Runner

Test Campaign Runner component has been successfully added to the Trail Network `{{tn_id}}`.

The runner is successfully registered to Keysight Test Campaign Manager `{{test_campaign_manager_url}}`

Runner name: `{{runner_name}}`

3.6.1.2 OPENCAPIF

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network? Yes, a Kubernetes cluster
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? No
 - Is the image of the virtual machine published in the sandbox marketplace?
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...)
 - Which networks? No
- Is this object going to be available for all sites? Yes
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks? No
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support?

Assumptions:

In every platform/testbed will be a CAPIF instance at core level to be shared by common services, but this object allows the deployment of a private CAPIF instance inside a trial network for testing purposes

Object information

Component Name: openCAPIF

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

| | |
|--------------|---|
| Dependencies | oneKE |
| Short Desc | CAPIF |
| Long Desc | This object deploys a OpenCAPIF instance inside a Trial Network |
| Hypervisors | [one] |
| Sites | [uma, focus, Athens, oulu] |

Public Object Input Parameters:

Public variables are those whose value can be modified from the TNLCM portal.

Required input parameters add information that can't be set with defaults, like dependencies with other deployed components.

Variable types are currently int, str, intlist and strlist.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|------------------|--------------------------------|------|---------------|---------|---------------|
| capif_kubeconfig | Kubernetes cluster config file | str | true | | true |

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Value |
|----------------|-------------------|------|-------|
| | | | |

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values or values generated during execution

| Output Parameter Name | Short Description | Example Value |
|-----------------------|---|---------------------------------------|
| capif_core_url | Url where OpenCAPIF core service is exposed | capif.aki8s.6gsandbox.uma.internal |
| capif_core_port | OpenCAPIF listen port | 443 |
| capif_register_url | Url where OpenCAPIF register service is exposed | register.aki8s.6gsandbox.uma.internal |
| capif_register_port | OpenCAPIF listen port | 443 |

3.6.1.2 RADIO NOKIA UMA

Preliminary questions:

- Does this object need to deploy infrastructure within the trial network?
 - No. It is about HW deployed into UMA testbed laboratory
 - Does this object need to deploy a virtual machine image? No
- Is this object going to use the site's shared networks? (NTN, monitoring, internet, ...) Yes
 - Which networks? Nokia Radio UMA Network
- Is this object going to be available for all sites? No, only at UMA
- Is this object limited in being able to be instantiated in multiple simultaneous trial networks? Yes
 - How many simultaneous instances does it support? 1

Assumptions:

The Nokia Radio is a physical equipment that nowadays we are not able to modify configuration in real time.

Within this scenario, we decided to define a static configuration that must be pre provisioned into the Nokia Radio before being able to use this component in a trial network.

This forces us to make a very inflexible definition of the object, something that will happen with most physical equipment that wants to be integrated into trial networks.

In the specific case of the Nokia Radio, the previous configuration will consist of the election of a PLNMN, TAC, SNSSAI and the IP of the AMF, and static routes to reach the TN-

Object information

Component Name: Radio Nokia UMA

Component metadata:

Informational values formatted and displayed in the TNLCM to the experimenter. The name of maintainers will be only included in the 6G-Library Repository (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/>).

| | |
|--------------|--|
| Dependencies | 5G_CORE, Nokia_Radio_UMA_Network |
| Short Desc | Radio Nokia UMA |
| Long Desc | This component allows the use of a real Nokia Radio into a Trial Network. The configuration exposed by this component should be synced with the 5G core and the UE to be used in conjunction with it |
| Hypervisors | [one] |
| Sites | [uma] |

Public Object Input Parameters:

Public variables are those whose value can be modified from the TNLCM portal.

Required input parameters add information that can't be set with defaults, like dependencies with other deployed components.

Variable types are currently int, str, intlist and strlist.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Type | Default Value | Choices | Required When |
|----------------|---|------|----------------------|---------|---------------|
| reserved_from | From date where the component is to be reserved | str | YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ | | true |
| reserved_to | To date where the component is to be reserved | str | YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ | | true |

Private Object Defaults:

Private variables are those that are necessary for the deployment of the component but whose value cannot be modified from the TNLCM portal.

They can be used to define static configurations. Values used during the deployment of each component.

Because of static pre configuration, this params should be managed as private.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Value |
|----------------|---------------------------------------|--------------|
| plmn_id | PLMN preconfigured on the Nokia Radio | 21438 |
| tac | Tracking area code | 20 |
| snsnsai_sst | Slice service type | 1 |
| snsnsai_sd | Slice differentiator | 1 |
| amf_ip | AMF IP | 10.90.5.10 |
| route_amf_via | Route to AMF via IP | 10.11.28.200 |

Object Output Values:

Component values to be made available to the TNLCM in future object deployments into the same Trial Network. Other components can use them.

Output values can be input values, private values of values generated during execution.

| Parameter Name | Short Description | Value |
|---------------------|---|---|
| reserved_range_time | Range of dates between which the component will be reserved | from:YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ,to: YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SS |
| plmn_id | PLMN preconfigured on the Nokia Radio | 21438 |
| tac | Tracking area code | 20 |
| snssai_sst | Slice service type | 1 |
| snssai_sd | Slice differentiator | 1 |
| amf_ip | AMF IP | 10.90.5.10 |
| route_amf_via | IP route to AMF | 10.11.28.200 |

Object Deployment Results:

It is necessary to create a jinja template from the markdown file that we will use as an output report when deploying the component. It must contain all the relevant information about the component itself so that the experimenter can use it.

NOKIA RADIO UMA

NOKIA RADIO UMA component has been successfully added to the Trial Network {{ tn_id }}

Important information:

This component will be available:

from: {{ date_from }}

to: {{ date_to }}

Relevant information about Radio Configuration

- PLMN: {{ plmn_id }}
- TAC: {{ tac }}
- S-NSSAI SST: {{ snssai_sst }}
- S-NSSAI SD: {{ snssai_sd }}
- AMF IP: {{ amf_ip }}
- ROUTE AMF VIA: {{ router_ip }}

https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/blob/nokia_radio_uma/nokia_radio_uma/result_templates/ok_result.md.i2

4 INTEGRATION WITH 6G-SANDBOX LIBRARY

This Part of the deliverable will include the integration approaches of API, experimentation automation tools and trial network lifecycle manager, and 6G repository with the 6G-SANDBOX Library. In this version, we intentionally skip this part, and it will be added in the next version of this deliverable.

5 CONCLUSION

This document presents an overview of the initial release of the 6G Library, providing insights into the essential technology enablers that are integral to its operations. These enablers include Open RAN, RIS, NTN (incorporating OpenSAND), deterministic networking utilizing P4 and TSN, and XR. We explore the fundamental concepts behind these technology enablers and clarify their respective roles within the 6G Library. Additionally, the document meticulously details the procedures for implementing these technologies, offering perspectives on network components, configurations, deployment scenarios, and practical use cases. Moreover, we mention the 6G library object component for each technology. Looking ahead to future versions of this deliverable, we will elaborate on the integration methodologies of these innovative technologies with the 6G-SANDBOX library.

REFERENCES

- [1] O-RAN Alliance, available at: <https://www.o-ran.org/>
- [2] M. Polese, L. Bonati, S. D’Oro, S. Basagni and T. Melodia, "Understanding O-RAN: Architecture, Interfaces, Algorithms, Security, and Research Challenges," in IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 1376-1411, Second Quarter 2023, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2023.3239220. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10024837>
- [3] Cloud Native O-RAN Geolocation Solution and the Seamless Transition to 5G SA, available at: <https://www.virtualexhibition.o-ran.org/classic/generation/2023/category/open-ran-demonstrations/sub/open-cloud/327>
- [4] O-RAN next Generation Research Group (nGRG) Research Report (14 Dec 2023), available at: https://mediastorage.o-ran.org/ngrg-rr/nGRG-RR-2023-01-O-RAN-Towards-6G-v1_3.pdf
- [5] Sustainable development Goal – United Nations - <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- [6] 5G & Non-terrestrial networks, 5G Americas whitepaper, February 2022
- [7] Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) for NR Phase 3 - https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/tsg_ran/TSG_RAN/TSGR_102/Docs/RP-234073.zip
- [8] P. Bosshart, D. Daly, G. Gibb, M. Izzard, N. Mckeown, J. Rexford, C. Schlesinger, D. Talayco, A. Vahdat, G. Varghese, and D. Walker, "P4: Programming Protocol-Independent Packet Processors," ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review, 2014.

- [9] "ONF SDN Evolution." [Online]. Available: www.opennetworking.org
- [10] "In-band Network Telemetry (INT) Dataplane Specification Version 2.1." [Online]. Available: https://p4.org/p4-spec/docs/INT_v2_1.pdf
- [11] IEEE Standard for Local and Metropolitan Area Networks—Bridges and Bridged Networks – Amendment 31: Stream Reservation Protocol (SRP) Enhancements and Performance Improvements," 802.1 WG - Higher Layer LAN Protocols Working Group, 2018.
- [12] 3GPP TS 23.501 "System Architecture for the 5G System (5GS)", v16.18.0," https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/Specs/archive/23_series/23.501/23501-gi0.zip.
- [13] Mann, S., and Wyckoff, C., "Extended Reality", MIT 4-405, 1991.
- [14] M. Slater "Place illusion and plausibility can lead to realistic behaviour in immersive virtual environments". *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 364(1535):3549–3557, 2009.
- [15] A. T. Hinds, I. D. Curcio, and M. Hamilton, "Immersive media and the metaverse," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 9, pp. 48–54, 2023.
- [16] G. Minopoulos and K. E. Psannis, "Opportunities and challenges of tangible xr applications for 5g networks and beyond," *IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine*, 2022
- [17] 3GPP TR 26.928, "Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Extended Reality (XR) in 5G"
- [18] MACOM, 'Design with PIN Diodes'. MACOM. Accessed: May 30, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://cdn.macom.com/applicationnotes/AG312.pdf>
- [19] 3GPP, "ETSI TS 138 101-2." ETSI. Accessed: May 31, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/138100_138199/13810102/17.05.00_60/ts_13810102v170500p.pdf
- [20] W. Tang et al., 'Path Loss Modeling and Measurements for Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces in the Millimeter-Wave Frequency Band', *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 70, no. 9, pp. 6259–6276, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TCOMM.2022.3193400.
- [21] Z. Li, H. Hu, J. Zhang, and J. Zhang, 'RIS-Assisted mmWave Networks With Random Blockages: Fewer Large RISs or More Small RISs?', *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 986–1000, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1109/TWC.2022.3200157.
- [22] OWO gitbook: <https://owo-game.gitbook.io/owo-api/>